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AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

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Summary

This document includes the 6 national recommendations papers developed by IMMERSE partner countries: Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Spain. The policy papers discuss IMMERSE research results at national level and provide recommendations addressed to policy makers and the educational sector.

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1 National recommendations papers on refugee and migrant children's integration

Introduction

This deliverable presents the 6 National Recommendations Papers drafted by IMMERSE research partners from 6 European countries: Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Spain. It is part of the WP4, Task 4.3, aimed at the production of a set of recommendations at national level addressed to national policymakers and the educational sector.

Based on a shared methodology and template, partners conducted research to collect contextual data and summarize the national policies related to migration and the inclusion of minors with a migratory background in the educational sector and in the society. Following, partners discussed IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators and analysed the main evidence and critical issues emerged from national data collection¹, qualitative insights and good practices. Finally, recommendations have been formulated to provide practical tools and suggestions to improve stakeholders' daily work and produce a positive social impact. Children have been actively involved in the co-creation and formulation of policy asks through consultation activities that guaranteed an active participation and an effective listening of their voices.

¹ Partners analysed the data available at the time of drafting (up to 30th April 2023).

2 National recommendation paper – Belgium: The socio-educational integration of migrant-background minors in Belgium: evidence and policy recommendations from IMMERSE project

Authors: Katherine Shea and Farzana S. Islam – Active Citizen Europe

2.1 Executive summary

This policy paper aims to review the indicators, the results of the analysed survey data, and consultation efforts from the IMMERSE Project in Belgium, to highlight good practices by macro, meso and micro level stakeholders regarding the socio-educational integration of migrant children into Belgian schools and other learning environments. It further aims to make policy recommendations on policy areas where Belgian government education authorities, educational institutions and all stakeholders involved in working with migrant-background children could enact changes to the benefit of the integration process.

2.2 The Belgian context

In 2021 Belgium received 26,000 asylum applicants which was a 54% increase compared to 2020 and over 7,000 of these applicants were children. The main countries of origin for these applicants included Afghanistan and Syria (Desmée & Cebotari, 2023). Pressures are exacerbated by an influx of migrant children since the start of the Russo-Ukrainian war. In 2022 around 63,356 people fleeing Ukraine received temporary protection status in Belgium (EMN, 2023). By May 2022, c.30,000 refugees from Ukraine had registered, 37% of them being of school age. Eurostat estimates that the share of non-national children in the child population of Belgium is 12% - >16 % (EUROSTAT, 2023).

Belgium is a federal state constituted by language-based communities/territorial regions; Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels Capitol Region. Schooling is mandatory for children between 5 and 18 in Belgium, irrespective of residence status. Each community has competency over education and the two main language regions (Dutch and French) have adapted a pedagogical approach of DASPA (French) and OKAN (Dutch) classes for migrant or asylum-seeking children. In primary schools in the Dutch system, individual schools decide how to structure OKAN, either in mainstream classes or as separate classes. In the French primary system, separate DASPA classes are required until competency is ensured. From secondary school (c. age 12), in both systems OKAN/DASPA classes are segregated classes. They focus on the linguistic competency of migrant students before encountering subject classes. This has drawbacks for integration; newly arrived children are isolated from mainstream schooling and from chances to socially mix with non-migrant children.

There are problems due to transience and unstable housing situations, for instance for Unaccompanied Migrant Minors (UAMs). There can be a lack of adequate public transport (Kinderrechtencoalitie Vlaanderen, 2018) and children can be transferred between language communities during asylum proceedings which interferes with linguistic acquisition and educational progress.

There is a shortage of teachers in Belgium and a shortage of OKAN/DASPA classes (Vlaamsparlament, 2023). The problems encountered in the transition from reception classes to mainstream education are evident in an attainment gap between migrant and non-migrant children, one of the highest in Europe. This is exacerbated by high rates of poverty amongst migrant children who are often concentrated in disadvantaged communities (Schleicher, 2018). PISA reports reflect the fact that educational attainment levels are high, yet there continues to be a problem of equity (Schleicher, 2018). Factors such as migration background and socio-economic status still have a strong determining relationship with students' educational achievements and trajectories.

Despite teacher training in subject skills, as well as training that includes courses on sustainability and diversity, teachers are often not fully equipped to address the specific learning needs of students from migration backgrounds. In OKAN and DASPA classes, teachers are generally highly skilled and attuned to the needs of their students. In mainstream academic, technical and vocational education teachers are often less versed in methods that address certain classroom learning needs of migrant children. Some communities (i.e. City of Mechelen) have made progress in improving integration and educational attainment through targeted progressive policies across communities and schools, but these initiatives are not broadly adopted across Belgium.

2.3 IMMERSE project: evidence-based considerations and critical issues

IMMERSE is a European project² aimed at understanding how effectively children of migrant origin are integrated in different educational systems in 6 countries: Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Spain. The project consulted available information sources and carried out a large-scale survey based on IMMERSE dashboard of indicators to explore different areas of the life of children and adolescents in these countries.

IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators

The IMMERSE dashboard was developed in the preliminary stages, based on a co-creation process: opinions of migrant and refugee children and their families, and people in close contact with them in schools, NGOs and at policymaking level were accessed via workshops, focus groups and interviews to explore these stakeholders' direct experiences to obtain a meaningful definition of integration. The Dashboard consolidates the main parameters that have been collected and analysed regarding the socio-educational integration of migrant children in the six participating European host countries to be accessible to all stakeholders and to provide a cross-cultural framework for investigating integration policies for migrant children in educational settings across countries. The indicators cover fundamental aspects at the three levels of integration: micro level (children and their families), meso level (education centres, educational communities and neighbourhoods) and macro level (broader civil society and its institutions).

² For more information, please visit <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/>

The final version of the IMMERSE dashboard³ is based on 30 indicators, specifically 14 for integration outcomes and 16 for promoting and impeding factors for integration outcomes. The results of integration (outcomes) are divided into five dimensions (access to rights, language and culture, well-being, social connection and educational achievement), while the factors facilitating or opposing integration (determinants) are instead linked to the areas of leadership politics, school segregation, learning support, mental health services, negative attitudes, school organisation and teachers.

Data collection results for Belgium

IMMERSE data collection took place in formal (primary and secondary schools) and non-formal (such as after-school programs) educational environments. It aimed to investigate the interaction between students, educators, and the community in which learning took place. IMMERSE sought to identify and measure key areas for intervention to help students reach their potential and to establish bridges between people from different cultures, thus contributing to building more supportive and cohesive societies.

In Belgium, 1,272 children completed the IMMERSE surveys, with a significantly higher number of Older Children (10-18) participating, comprising 92% of survey takers, than Younger Children (7-9) who comprised 8% of the responses. The 22% were non-migrant children, while the largest portion of answers came from students who identified as first-generation migrants (40%) with second generation migrants representing another 38%. Respondents identified their gender as 50% female, 48% male and 2% in another way. Developmental stage at the time of the survey was broken down into 5 categories.

And participants recorded their current education level at the time of the surveys as: Secondary school 81%, Primary school 14%, taking courses/classes but not in a regular Secondary school 4%, not in any kind of education right now 1%.

The majority of first-generation children are born in Belgium, while a percentage above 1% of respondents come from 35 different countries⁴.

Integration outcomes⁵

The majority of migrant-background children survey respondents in Belgium (62%) declare a high competence in French or Dutch, but it is a relatively small majority. One third of the migrant-background children in Belgium (32%) declare a medium competence in French or Dutch.

On a positive note, more than half of all responding migrant-background children in Belgium (58%) feel close to both their cultures of origin (parents' country/countries of origin, language or religion) as well as to other groups of people. This is the largest percentage across IMMERSE countries

³ To discover the IMMERSE dashboard, please visit: <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/selection-and-creation-of-dashboard-of-socio-educational-integration-indicators/>

⁴ The highest number came from Bulgaria (13%) followed by Ukraine (19%), Afghanistan (9%), Spain (8%) and Syria (5%). The Republic of Columbia, Eritrea, Ghana, Morocco and the Netherlands each made up 4%, followed by Turkey at 3%, Albania, France, Guinea, Iran, Poland and Somalia at 2%. Each of the eighteen remaining countries were identified as the country of birth of 1% of respondents; 5 of these within the EU (Germany, Italy, Portugal, Romania and Slovakia), the rest from the rest of Europe/Asia (Russia, Armenia, State of Palestine, Iraq, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines), Africa (Democratic Republic of Congo, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal), and North and South America (U.S.A, Brazil).

⁵ Results are referred to migrant-background children.

(average 45%), suggesting that Belgian integration policies and actions might have effectively worked. Considering the gender variable, the percentage of children feeling close to people from both the culture of origin and other groups of people is larger for girls (64%) than boys (55%), although the difference is small. The percentage is notably smaller though for children who define their gender "in another way" (47%).

Nonetheless, a smaller proportion (13%) feel close to their cultures of origin exclusively. Moreover, almost one third of them (29%) do not feel close to their cultures of origin. This is probably connected to the fact that most migrant-background respondents are born and grow up in Belgium, developing a strong connection with the local culture.

At a personal level, only over one third of migrant-background children in Belgium (35%) declare a high level of feeling of belonging in their schools. This percentage is notably below the average (48%) and the lowest across IMMERSE countries. The majority (58%) declare a medium level of belonging. Moreover, the majority of migrant-background children in Belgium declare being quite or very happy (82%), but still 18% declare feeling not very or not at all happy.

Half of the migrant-background children in Belgium (52%) declare a high level of support from friends and peers. Only a marginal proportion declare a low level of support (8%), although this is the highest among IMMERSE countries (average 5%) and equal to Italy.

Similarly, half of the migrant-background children in Belgium (51%) declare a high level of support from teachers. In contrast, only a small proportion declare a low level of support (7%), which is slightly more than most other IMMERSE countries (average 5%).

Teachers and schools are clearly trusted by slightly more than half of the migrant-background children in Belgium (55%), but still one out of five migrant-background children (18%) distrust teachers and schools.

Beyond the school environment, the health system is the most trusted among the migrant-background children in Belgium, followed by the educational system and the police and justice system. Doctors and hospitals are trusted by the majority of these children in Belgium (69%). Police and the justice system are trusted by over half of the migrant-background children in Belgium (55%).

Integration barriers and facilitators

Studying the experience of bullying, the 44% of migrant-background children affirm that they have been bullied at some point. The percentage of migrant-background children who have been bullied is notably smaller for boys (39%) than girls (49%). The same is true for migrant-background children who defined their gender "in another way" (47%). The percentage of children who declare to have been bullied notably decreases with migrant-background: from 55% of native children, to 50% of second-generation migrant children and to 37% first-generation children. It is interesting to note that fewer migrant children reported being bullied than native children although this may be explained in part by the fact that many first generation migrant children are in segregated OKAN and DASPA classes. The difference between second generation and native children was less pronounced although still interesting to note that the former reported less bullying than the latter.

Only over 60% of the migrant-background children in Belgium attend language or learning support (either at school or in their neighbourhood).

Among migrant-background children, 45% declare participating in after-school learning or language support in their school and outside of schools. The percentage of girls who use supplemental language or learning support is smaller (56%) than boys (66%) and that of children who define their gender "in another way" (64%).

Considering extra-curricular activities (such as sport, music, art, etc.), the percentage of migrant-background children who attend them at their school or neighbourhood is nearly 60%, highlighting the good but still insufficient offer of support activities. It diminishes from boys (65%) to girls (54%), and even more so from children who define their gender "in another way" (33%).

Qualitative insights

To evaluate more in depth the socio-educational processes of integration in Belgium, qualitative research activities were carried out. Data was acquired from the cities of Mechelen and Brussels via photovoice samples.

In the former, the Photovoice sample was composed of male and female students, aged 12-16 attending secondary school in Mechelen. They lived with their families and had all arrived in Belgium in the last five to ten years from the war in Syria. The themes that dominated their responses as important for creating a sense of inclusion, belonging and integration were the following. Schools, youth organisations and leisure activities were seen as places that could foster friendship and increase feelings of belonging. Links to culture of origin were deemed important to maintain, while leisure activities including those run by schools were seen as fundamental for promoting well-being. Educational settings (both primary and secondary) were found to be key for fostering community and a sense of belonging.

In the latter, participants were a mix of male and female students aged 12-18, all attending OKAN classes in secondary school in Belgium. They lived with their families in the city of Brussels and had arrived from Ukraine, Rwanda, Spain, Columbia, Turkey and Moldova. Responses were similar but additionally included the need for access to nature, opportunities within educational settings to share memories, and chances to achieve in school as important for fostering belonging and integration.

Teachers, principals, policymakers and other stakeholders indicated problems inherent to the Belgium school system that are barriers to integration. Lack of financial resources, teacher shortages, lack of intercultural learning material, lack of support in the transition from reception/bridging classes to mainstream education, linguistic barriers for migrant families due to language policies, particularly in Flanders, were amongst issues raised in qualitative interviews.

Good practices

Partners identified 60 good practices aimed at inclusive education and social innovation at local, national or EU level, to develop ideas and methods for a common model of integration and a more

welcoming school for minors with a migration background⁶. Good practices were analysed for efficacy, political relevance, efficiency, reproducibility and transferability.

Each proposed good practice corresponded to one or more of the indicators in the project's Dashboard and most aimed to promote access to and completion of formal education for children of a migration background. They aimed to promote skills acquisition such as language, and to provide cultural support to improve belonging and relationships. Most sought to increase children's sense of belonging and some aimed to develop innovative approaches for greater inclusion, new models of governance and intercultural teaching methodologies with child-centred education.

From co-curricular support for academics and language to vocational training and leisure activities, good practices encompassed a broad range of actors from sectors such as health, research and education, from organisations, schools, NGO's, universities and government institutions. Good practices were therefore mapped with an interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder approach.

The identified projects were recipients for private, governmental, or European funding.

Good Practices in Belgium

Groep Intro is a non-profit organisation committed to working towards an inclusive society. It works across towns and cities in Flanders working on projects in the labour market, in schools, in the justice system, in communities and in leisure activities. Groep Intro engages Youth Workers who work with young people at risk of social exclusion, including those in the Secondary School OKAN classes both in schools and in the communities. An example of a project is CHILLweek in Mechelen aimed specifically at children from migrant backgrounds. In the Spring break of 2019, 40 young people, between 12 and 18 years old from the various OKAN classes, were introduced to Mechelen leisure activities. CHILLweek was an initiative of the municipality of Mechelen, in collaboration with the Agentschap Integratie & Inburgering and Groep Intro. Groep Intro also works on projects in part-time and apprenticeship education, including dual-learning, and offers individual coaching and initial training and work experience for young people, providing access and information for accessing the local labour market. The financing comes from within, but additional local subsidies enable project extensions.

2.4 Policy implications and recommendations

Based on IMMERSE research results, we strongly recommend to the Belgian Government the adoption of a cohesive federal policy with regards to integration approaches in education across educational authorities, so that the approaches to integration are at best streamlined and, at the very least, complementary. This implies that the Flemish Educational Authority (Vlaams Onderwijs) and the French-speaking Education Authority (Fédération Wallonie) must work together to find some common approaches to support integration of children from a migration background which are underpinned with the following considerations.

From a regional policy level we recommend to the Vlaams Onderwijs en Vorming and the Federation Wallonie, who have competency over education in their regions, that the general

⁶ This summarises the results of the analysis available in the publication IMMERSE (2022). All 60 good practices can be found in IMMERSE's Online Digital Database <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/online-digital-database-of-good-practices-and-resources-in-social-integration-of-refugee-and-migrant-children/>

syllabuses for schools should be reviewed and revised from an intercultural education perspective. This means that subjects should not be taught exclusively through a strictly Belgo-centric lens. The long-standing tendency to teach subjects from a single perspective should be challenged and revisited. This should be introduced early, in primary and secondary education, by already including other perspectives.⁷ In countries such as Belgium where a large portion of migrant-origin children have roots in European ex-colonies (such as Congo and Morocco), this intercultural approach will be critical in acknowledging and validating different experiences and perspectives from the past, and together building a common facing future. This recommendation requires a commitment to a principle of openness which must be embedded into teacher training at all stages.

We strongly recommend to both the education authorities that, from an educational policy approach to integration, a new more multi-language approach should underpin classroom practice. We recommend that educational institutions should adopt a pedagogical approach based on openness and positivity towards all the mother tongues represented in the classroom and this may require a top-down policy initiative. This approach would increase feelings of belonging and acceptance amongst non-Belgian or migrant-origin Belgian children in education by removing any alienation or stigma suffered by speakers of other languages (both students and their families). Host languages should be valued as an educational tool, rather than being viewed as a hindrance to accessing host language skills.

We recommend that both federal and regional governments address the clear need for investment in the education of specialised teacher training programmes for both OKAN/DASPA and mainstream teachers. Furthermore, we recommend that authorities pursue a policy that every school should be expected to offer basic access to OKAN and DASPA services in every locality, so that schools share the responsibility for integrating migrant children.

We recommend that the Vlaams Overheid and Gouvernement Wallon, address much needed structural changes to the system of allocating schools and housing, and look to policies for increasing the availability of long-term, low-cost, social housing which would reduce transience and ensure that children are less likely to be moved between language communities. We strongly recommend co-ordination between regional and local governments, reception centres and agencies and education institutions to reduce the need for migrant children to change schools during asylum proceedings.

In pursuing these ends, we recommend that the regional education authorities adopt new policies for teacher training, so that institutions can pursue training courses that deliver methodologies that aid integration, accessible to all teachers, including specialist subject teachers. For integration to be successful, intercultural education should be embedded in the professional training and development of teachers throughout their professional careers. This approach to initial and continuing teacher training would enhance trust between teachers and students, an element that seemed to be particularly lacking in regular secondary classrooms, beyond OKAN and DASPA dedicated classrooms.

⁷ Examples of ways to do this include reading books by non-European and especially Global South writers; considering and validating historical events through perspectives of both colonisers and the colonised; exploring Greek and Arab roots in maths and science, Mesopotamian contributions to law, ancient Egyptian contributions to gym class in the form of hula hoops, etc

We recommend that all people working within the sphere of education - emanating down from federal and regional policy makers to school leaders and teachers - should be equipped with cultural sensitivity and openness training in order to create an understanding and receptive classroom environment. When outreach to parents is strong in schools, feelings of belonging and integration for children improve.⁸

Finally, we recommend to education institutions and practitioners that classroom policies and planned learning outcomes should begin with an approach that explicitly puts each child, and the range of his or her lived experiences, identities and worldviews, at the centre. This “whole-child approach” and the principles of “care and compassion” is seen to significantly impact on well-being. This incorporates a nurturing of all aspects of the child and strengthens his or her foundations in self and society. This requires both a pedagogic and pastoral approach to education and requires specific intercultural training for local authority officials, leaders, teachers and support staff. It is crucial to also engage foreign-language speaking parents and guardians. This clearly means that, at the governmental level, financial resources should be earmarked to support training for this approach, and policy goals should be explicit, so that school regulations and guidelines can be enacted.

Children’s recommendations for inclusive schools and societies

Based on preliminary findings, consultations were undertaken in Belgium as a focus group with 12 OKAN students aged 12-17 from Turkey, Spain, Ukraine, Columbia, Moldova and Rwanda, and their teacher. This addressed early findings to receive feedback from students about what they feel could improve some of the less positive Belgian statistics.

They suggested that school communities in Belgium could improve happiness in school with more social and entertainment activities (movie nights, sports, dances), a greater emphasis on teaching content that explores global topics, more fun learning activities (such as kahoot).

Newcomer students could be helped to feel more supported by fellow students by having more mixing events with mainstream classes and OKAN/DASPA classes, including trips to museums and sport tournaments, encouraging opportunities for communication between OKAN/DASPA and mainstream students. This cohort said that school systems in Belgium could be easier to trust if there was less of a “chasm” between teachers and students – that teachers should be less subject-focused and more aware of psychological needs of students. Lessons could involve less teacher talking and writing, and more interactive work, such as games or discussions. Teachers could better support newcomer students if they made sure that they were approachable and tried to make the class interesting.

Students felt that more openness to the different languages of the students could make both students and teachers more comfortable with each other, and that teachers could develop a better understanding of each student individually. Students said that trust could be built with

⁸ This is confirmed by other projects, such as Intereg SIREE project that was conducted in Belgian schools where teachers, parents and students recorded the benefits for all stakeholders in programmes that encouraged regular outreach to, and communication opportunities with, parents of children from migrant backgrounds, and facilitated new approaches to learning, such as increased sensitivity from both sides to different cultural norms during physical education classes. Forums to engage with migrant parents, with translators or in a common language that is spoken which may not be the host language, helped to facilitate group meetings.

teachers if they are kind and can talk openly about problems and varying situations of the students, and if teachers are willing to listen. Students felt that teachers could be less insistent on repeating information in Dutch but find other languages in common (English was cited) to explain to aid Dutch language development. School communities could prevent and try to end bullying by instilling an awareness of how people are different, teachers should directly warn parents about not tolerating bullying and schools would need to openly talk about problems to address them.

2.5 Conclusions

The results of IMMERSE quantitative and qualitative research have identified some of the particular challenges that the integration of migrant children into the two main Belgian education systems presents. Problems such as language acquisition are sometimes exacerbated by an asylum system that is federal in nature but school systems that are regional, while OKAN and DASPA schools do not always provide the best method of integration into school cultures. Data reveals a need to do more to promote happiness and belonging in schools, trust in teachers and in school systems and feelings of support from teachers and peers. The implementation of a more federal approach to educational policy may help. Belgian classrooms are increasingly diverse and attainment gaps in academic achievement additionally need to be addressed. Some intercultural educational approaches are identified but these need to be normalised across curriculums and age categories in schools. Regarding languages, the need for competency in the language of pedagogy may be better approached by better allowances for those whose language skills are still developing. This has implications for governmental policy objectives, organisation of teacher training institutions. Classroom, subject and OKAN/DASPA teachers all require funding and training as to facilitate better transitions from reception/bridging education into mainstream classes. All teachers should have training that provides awareness and strategies to address the particular linguistic and cultural demands of their subject(s) for non-native students. Additionally, it is fundamental to enabling parents to find ways to engage with the school, despite a linguistic barrier. Finally, there is an urgent need to put the well-being of the child as a central tenet in education, with all the cultural/historical/language sensitivity and requisite training that it entails.

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3 National recommendations paper – Germany: The socio-educational integration of refugee and migrant-background children in Germany: evidence and policy proposals from the IMMERSE project

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3.1 Executive summary

Against the backdrop of current national realities, this policy paper aims to analyse and put into context the results of the quantitative data arising from the IMMERSE survey and the qualitative fieldwork in Germany. Its primary objectives are to highlight the results and to provide country-specific policy recommendations for Germany to further improve the socio-educational integration and inclusion of refugee and migrant children and young people in schools and other educational environments.

3.2 The German context

In 2022, 23.8 million of the total 83.1 million inhabitants in Germany had a migration background (immigrants and their descendants) - this corresponds to a share of 28.7% of the total population. Of the 23.8 million people, 12.2 million were German citizens and 11.6 million were foreigners. The largest share of people with a migration background in 2022 were people from other European countries. The 31.8% came from one of the 26 other member states of the EU and the 29.8% from another European state. Most of the persons with a migrant background in 2022 came from Turkey (11.9%/2.8 million), followed by Poland (9.2%/2.2 million), Russia (5.7%/1.4 million), and Romania (4.6%/1.1 million). Kazakhstan and Syria are the most important non-European countries of origin, with shares of 5.6 and 5.1% (1.3 and 1.2 million, respectively) (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2023a).

According to the Federal Statistical Office (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2023b), the Russo-Ukrainian war has caused a sharp increase in inflows from Ukraine compared to previous years. In 2022, about 1,098,000 arrivals of people from Ukraine were registered in Germany. After the beginning of the war, both the gender ratio and the age structure of the Ukrainian population in Germany has changed significantly compared to previous years. Among the Ukrainian refugees newly registered in Germany since the end of February 2022, children are disproportionately represented (34% under the age of 18) (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2023b).

The Federal Agency for Civic Education (2023) projects that the proportion of people with a migration background in Germany will continue to increase in the medium term. In fact, in 2022, 41.6% of all children under 5 already had a migration background.

Given this data, it is important to underscore that children from families with a migrant background are especially vulnerable to educational disadvantages. According to the findings of the Autorinnengruppe Bildungsberichterstattung (2022), the three risk factors for education – the risk

of parents with low formal qualifications, the social risk factor, and the financial risk factor – affect some population groups in particular. As in previous years, children from families with a migration background are disproportionately affected by risk situations. 48% of them grow up under the burden of at least one risk situation, compared to only 16% of children without a migration background. Of all three risk situations, 8% of children with a migration background are affected, while only 1% of children without a migration background are affected.

What is more, 47,500 young people ended their school careers without a diploma in 2022, according to the latest education survey commissioned by the Bertelsmann Foundation. Another finding of the Gütersloh study is that this has not changed since 2011, which is as far back as the study extends. The two most important risk factors have also always remained the same: migration background and poverty. Also, significant and unchanged is that boys are more at risk than girls (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2023).

Since 1945 Germany has produced migration and integration policies that are as complex as they are ambivalent. If we summarise the years from 1945 until now, we see an alternation of necessary openness and unnecessary strain on the part of politics. In 2007, the National Integration Plan was adopted at the second Integration Summit. The plan's declared aim was to place integration initiatives by the federal government, the states, local authorities, and civil society on a common footing for the first time (Bundeszentrale, 2007). It cannot be denied that there has been progress in the socio-educational inclusion of refugee and migrant children. However, to this day Germany displays a federal fragmentation of integration policy. What is more, the German school system has faced persistent and politically unanswered challenges over the past two decades, including a chronic shortage of teachers⁹, inadequate infrastructure, particularly in terms of digital resources¹⁰, and urban gentrification along with the concentration of social disadvantages in certain city areas (Deutsches Schulportal der Robert Bosch Stiftung, 2023; Müller-Lancé, 2023). According to Beierle et al. (2019), in such communities, the vertical social and ethnic stratification of the population becomes horizontally 'spatialized'. This process can lead to a concentration of social risks/problems in individual neighbourhoods. The schools located in these neighbourhoods are also problematic because they are also exposed to a spiral of segregation.

3.3 IMMERSE project: evidence-based considerations and critical issues

IMMERSE¹¹ is a European project with the goal of assessing the effectiveness of the integration of refugee children and of migrant origin within the educational systems of six countries: Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Spain. The project carried out a comprehensive analysis of available information sources and conducted an extensive survey using key indicators, which were initially developed and made accessible through the IMMERSE dashboard. This survey aimed to investigate various aspects of the lives of children and adolescents in these countries. Workshops, focus groups, and interviews were employed to tap into the direct experiences of these stakeholders, ensuring a meaningful and holistic definition of integration.

IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators

⁹ Deutsches Schulportal der Robert Bosch Stiftung [German School Dashboard of the Robert Bosch Foundation]. 2023

¹⁰ Müller-Lancé. 2023.

¹¹ <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/>

The development of the IMMERSE dashboard followed a co-creation process, involving the insights and perspectives of migrant and refugee children, their families, as well as individuals closely connected to them within schools, NGOs, and policymaking circles. The Dashboard serves as a comprehensive repository of key parameters collected and analysed concerning the socio-educational integration of migrant children across the six European host countries participating in the project. Its purpose is to make this information accessible to all stakeholders and to establish a cross-cultural framework for the examination of integration policies for migrant children within educational contexts across different countries.

The indicators¹² within the Dashboard encompass critical aspects at three distinct levels of integration: the micro level (children and their families), the meso level (educational institutions, educational communities, and neighbourhoods), and the macro level (broader civil society and its institutions).

The final version of the IMMERSE Dashboard comprises 30 indicators, specifically 14 related to integration outcomes and 16 associated with promoting and hindering factors for integration. The outcomes are categorised into five dimensions, including access to rights, language and culture, well-being, social connections, and educational achievement. The determinants influencing integration outcomes are linked to areas such as leadership in politics, school segregation, learning support, mental health services, negative attitudes, school organisation, and teachers.

Data collection results for Germany

Integration outcomes

Most migrant-background children in Germany (67%) claim a high level of German proficiency, though it falls below the average for countries participating in the study. First-generation migrants have a lower proficiency compared to second-generation and non-migrant children (58%, 84%, and 90%, respectively), with proficiency increasing as children grow older.

A majority of migrant-background children in Germany (58%) feel close to both their cultures of origin and other groups, the highest percentage across participating countries. Conversely, around one third (32%) do not feel close to their cultures of origin, while a smaller group (10%) feels close exclusively to their cultures of origin. This pattern is consistent among both first- and second-generation migrant children. Around 43% of migrant-background children express a high sense of school belonging, which is slightly below the average for participating countries. While most of these children (76%) describe themselves as quite or very happy, a significant proportion (24%) also express not feeling very happy.

Migrant-background children in Germany indicate a high level of support from friends and peers (60%), slightly above the average for participating countries (54%). Second-generation migrant children receive the highest level of support from friends and peers (68%), followed by non-migrant children (58%) and first-generation migrant children (55%). Support from teachers is also reported, with half of the children (51%) reporting a high level of support, although it decreases with age among migrant-background children.

In Germany, trust in teachers and schools is expressed by slightly more than half of migrant-background children (56%), which is below the average for participating countries (66%). Distrust in teachers and schools is relatively high (17%). Trust levels vary between first-generation and

¹² <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/selection-and-creation-of-dashboard-of-socio-educational-integration-indicators/>

second-generation migrant children, with differences by gender and age. Doctors and hospitals are the most trusted institutions among migrant-background children in Germany (69%), although this trust level is below the average for participating countries (76%). Trust in doctors and hospitals varies by gender and decreases with age. Trust in the police and the justice system is also reported (55%), though it falls below the average for participating countries and decreases with age.

Integration barriers and facilitators

A significant minority (43%) of migrant-background children in Germany have experienced bullying, which exceeds the IMMERSE average (38%). Bullying experiences slightly decrease with migrant background: from 49% among native children to 45% for second-generation migrant children and 42% for first-generation children. Among migrant-background children, boys (39%) report slightly less bullying than girls (45%). However, children who define their gender in another way have been significantly more bullied (78%). Bullying experiences among migrant-background children notably decrease with age: from 50% among small children to 38% among late adolescents.

Around 43% of children avoid certain places due to fear of mistreatment, ranking above the IMMERSE average (40%). Nearly half of migrant-background children (49%) avoid places due to fear of mistreatment, which decreases slightly among non-migrant children (41%) and notably among second-generation migrant children (34%). The tendency to avoid places due to fear of mistreatment slightly decreases with age among migrant-background children: from 46% among small children to 39% among late adolescents.

The use of supplemental language or learning support services increases with migrant background, with significant differences: from 24% among native children and 40% among second-generation migrant children, up to 58% among first-generation children. Among migrant-background children, the use of these services notably decreases with age: from 64% among small children to 40% among late adolescents. Participation in extracurricular activities among migrant-background children decreases with age: from 71% among small children to 57% among late adolescents. Over two-thirds of migrant-background children in Germany (67%) participate in extracurricular activities, surpassing the average (61%) and ranking the highest among IMMERSE countries.

3.4 Policy implications and recommendations

Based on the qualitative research evidence, the consultation with young people, and survey data, the following policy recommendations addressed to policy makers and the educational sector have been elaborated, emphasising the importance of proactive measures to create an inclusive, respectful, and secure school environment for all students.

1. Allocating More Resources for German Language Learning

To facilitate language acquisition, we recommend Federal and state governments to provide schools with increased resources for teaching German. This includes additional qualified teachers, language support programs, and materials tailored to the diverse needs of students with varying language proficiencies. Adequate resources are vital for ensuring that students can effectively integrate into the German education system.

2. Promoting Native Languages

The Conference of Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs and the federal state ministries should recognize and promote the role of native languages within the school system. Providing

support for students to maintain and develop their native languages alongside learning German is crucial for their overall linguistic development. This support can include offering language classes, cultural activities, and materials in students' native languages. Schools should consider integrating non-European languages into their curricula. This not only enriches the educational experience but also promotes cultural diversity and a more comprehensive understanding of the world.

3. Diversity and Representation

Schools should actively recognize, celebrate, and foster diversity within their student body and staff. This includes acknowledging and respecting the diverse cultural backgrounds of students. Anchoring diverse cultural calendars in the school year can provide opportunities for cultural exchange and understanding. Additionally, promoting the teaching profession to both migrant and non-migrant populations can help create a more diverse and representative teaching workforce.

4. Enhancing Parental Involvement

Schools should actively involve parents in the language acquisition process of their children. This can be achieved through regular communication, parent-teacher conferences, and workshops that provide parents with strategies to support their children's language development at home. Creating avenues for parents to engage in their children's progress fosters a sense of partnership and community within the school.

5. Curriculum Changes for Inclusivity

The Conference of Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs and the federal state ministries should initiate assessments and clear changes to the curriculum, including textbooks, to present perspectives beyond the white European experience. This involves adopting an approach to education reflecting a more inclusive history and culture. Ensuring that students are exposed to a variety of perspectives is essential for their well-rounded education and understanding of the world.

6. Fostering a Respectful School Culture

Principals, teachers, and school staff should actively work towards cultivating a respectful school culture that values language, sensitivities, equality, and respect. This involves regular awareness programs and workshops for both students and staff to promote understanding and empathy. Schools should encourage open dialogue and empower students to speak up about any issues they encounter.

7. Gender-Sensitive and Age-Appropriate Approaches:

Teachers and school staff should be provided with guidelines by federal ministries and training by state institutes for teacher qualification to implement gender-sensitive and age-appropriate approaches in their interactions with students. These guidelines should promote inclusive practices that respect the diversity of students' backgrounds and identities, fostering an environment where everyone feels valued and understood.

8. Comprehensive Anti-Discrimination and Anti-Bullying Policies:

Federal ministries of education should establish comprehensive anti-discrimination, anti-bullying, and anti-racism policies and enable the school system in its entirety to implement them. They should be applied consistently across all levels of the education system, ensuring that every student is protected and feels safe. Schools should adopt zero-tolerance policies in all sensitive

areas, such as discrimination, bullying, and racism. Additionally, considering the establishment of a comprehensive code of conduct that outlines expected behaviours and consequences for breaches can provide a structured framework for maintaining a safe and inclusive school environment.

9. Community-based Safe Space for All:

Schools should prioritise their role as safe spaces for all students. To achieve this, investment in teacher training and professional development is essential. Educators should be equipped with the knowledge and skills to address discrimination and related issues effectively. Collaborative efforts with community organisations and the community itself can further enhance safety and promote a sense of belonging among students. (Porter and Cook, 2023)

Children's recommendations for inclusive schools and societies

Within the IMMERSE project, DOZ conducted policy consultations with migrant- and non-migrant-background young people in a secondary school in Leipzig¹³ which had previously participated in the IMMERSE quantitative data collection. The following are the young peoples recommendations for a more inclusive school and society:

- **Zero-Tolerance Policy:** Implement a clear and comprehensive zero-tolerance policy against discrimination, racism, and bullying in schools. This policy should outline specific actions that will not be tolerated, including hate speech, harassment, and physical aggression.
- **Accountability Measures:** Develop a system for holding individuals, including teachers and principals, accountable for addressing discrimination and bullying incidents. Ensure that they are trained in recognizing and addressing such issues promptly.
- **Respect-Centred Culture:** Develop and promote a school-wide culture centred around respect as a core value. Emphasise that respect should be the foundation of all interactions, both among students and between students and teachers.
- **Fair Assessment and Feedback:** Train teachers to provide fair assessments and feedback, recognizing that poor performance may be influenced by various factors. Encourage teachers to adopt an approach that supports and motivates students to improve rather than blame them.
- **Confidence-Building Sessions:** Implement regular confidence-building sessions between students and their class teachers. These sessions should provide a safe space for students to voice concerns, seek guidance, and build trust through open communication.

¹³ Two classes participated - an 8th grade with 17 young people aged 13 to 14 years old that had participated in the IMMERSE survey and a 9th grade with 19 young people 14 to 15 years old that had not participated in the IMMERSE survey. For the consultation, the young people were asked to write their own experiences with the topics racism, belonging, trust, language. In a second step they were asked to share their ideas of recommendation towards solutions of the problems. The input was then clustered by the facilitators.

- **Increased Dialogue:** Promote increased dialogue within the school community. Encourage students, teachers, and administrators to engage in open discussions about school culture, values, and issues that may affect it.
- **Racial Profiling Eradication:** Develop and enforce policies that explicitly prohibit racial profiling by law enforcement agencies. Provide training to officers on recognizing and avoiding biases in their interactions with the public.
- **Accountability Measures:** Implement robust accountability measures within police departments. This includes regular internal reviews of officer conduct, transparent reporting of incidents, and consequences for misconduct.

3.5 Conclusions

Over the course of the IMMERSE project both qualitative and quantitative research shed light on a number of problematic realities for refugee and migrant children. The main issues identified are racism, bullying, other forms of discrimination, a lack of respect and trust, and a fair number of problems with the police. The data clearly indicates a strong necessity to formulate national strategies for making the German education system inclusive on all levels. However, this undertaking requires a firm political commitment and dedicated funding. To create a more inclusive and equitable educational environment, it is imperative to implement comprehensive anti-discrimination and anti-bullying policies. These policies should be enforced rigorously to ensure the safety and well-being of all students. Simultaneously, fostering a respectful school culture should be a priority, where diversity is celebrated, and differences are embraced.

Furthermore, a critical aspect of inclusivity is the adoption of gender-sensitive and age-appropriate approaches in curriculum and classroom practices. Establishing community-based safe spaces for all students can also be instrumental in creating a supportive environment. Additionally, there should be a focus on promoting native languages and increasing resources for German language learning, which can help students from diverse backgrounds integrate more effectively. Lastly, enhancing parental involvement and increasing diversity and representation among educators and decision-makers will contribute to a more inclusive and equitable education system in Germany. These policies and practices collectively aim to ensure that every student feels valued, respected, and empowered in the educational setting.

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4 National recommendations paper – Greece: The socio-educational integration of migrant and refugee children in Greece: policy recommendations from IMMERSE H2020 project

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4.1 Executive summary

This policy paper reviews the indicators, the results of the analysed survey data, and consultation efforts from the IMMERSE project in Greece, highlighting good practices by macro, meso and micro level stakeholders in regard to the socio-educational integration of migrant children into Greek schools and other learning environments (informal educational settings). It aims at formulating policy recommendations on policy areas where the Greek government education authorities, educational institutions, international organizations' and NGO experts, and all stakeholders involved in working with migrant-background children, could enact changes to the benefit of the integration process.

4.2 The Greek context

According to the most recent census (2021), in Greece foreigners range from 810.000 to 940.000, and account for 7.4% to 8.4% of the population¹⁴ and it is estimated that over 15% of migrants are aged between 0-14. An estimate of 75% of refugee children have access to pre-school, primary and secondary education (statistics of the improved 2021/2022 year¹⁵). The percentage is higher for the participation of first- and second-generation migrant children.

Governmental integration strategies in Greece aim to increase the participation of refugee and migrant children in the education system, while striving to improving the living conditions of all

¹⁴ According to resident permits issued in December 2022 from the Ministry of Migration, the percentage is higher. The total permits issued were indeed 755,806 (out of which 222,000 EU citizens and expats, 472,000 third country nationals, 61,907 recognized refugees). Adding to those numbers 197,855 pending asylum requests, 2,588 requests for renewal for international protection and 22,316 new requests for international protection, plus 22,280 Ukrainian nationals under temporary EU protection, then the total number is 1,000,845, which accounts for 9,54% of the general population (10,482,487) (Census, 2021).

¹⁵ For more recent figures see UNICEF, Dec. 2022, showing a significant increase compared to the previous year, when rates were low overall and shockingly so in open accommodation centres (14 per cent attendance) and Reception and Identification Centres (less than one per cent). The increase in attendance reflects both the passing of the particular challenges caused by the Covid-19 pandemic response as well as emphasis in the government's efforts to increase attendance.

marginalised social groups¹⁶. Support in the form of additional specialised teaching staff is available to schools, who have high numbers of migrant students¹⁷.

However, the government of Greece has struggled to live up to its obligations to ensure that all refugee and migrant children are promptly enrolled in school and receive a quality education (AIDA, 2023)¹⁸. The main barriers in enrolment include the limited school capacity in urban areas¹⁹ and the lack of information by school Directors that all children, even the ones without regular residence (i.e. who are not included in the official reception system or are homeless) and children arriving in the middle of the school year, have the right to enrol. Another key issue relates to the access to schools due to constant changes in accommodation of refugee children.

The situation has gradually improved thanks to a normalisation of both asylum procedures and educational integration efforts of the government in cooperation with UNICEF, UNHCR and IOM (AIDA 2023). However, despite the positive steps undertaken by the Ministry of Education (MoE) during the school year 2021-2022, and the announcements made at the beginning of the school year 2022/2023 for an upgraded education system and improved school integration of refugee students, numerous shortcomings remain in school enrolment, attendance, and transportation to and from schools (e.g. from camps to urban areas). At the beginning of the school year 2022/2023, Greek Refugee Education Coordinators reported that a significant number of children with their families have moved within Greece, due to the termination of the ESTIA accommodation programme. This forced students to leave their school and enrol in new schools in other regions, disrupting their education and integration into the school community. Moreover, the new asylum application system introduced on 1st September 2022, is another hindrance to school enrolment and attendance. Lack of proof of asylum applications lodged electronically, until official registration at one of the Reception and Identification Centers (RICs), make children and their families 'invisible' to the state. The lack of legal documents appears to either discourage or prevent some families from enrolling their children to schools²⁰. Finally, families' fear of being deprived of their freedom

¹⁶ See Integration Strategies, Ministry of Migration and Asylum (MoMA). Social benefits are scarce. Since the end of the ESTIA programme in 2022, the Ministry of Migration covers a total of 5,120 applicants with CASH assistance (one third of needs) whereas accommodation is mostly camp based for newcomers. This is an important barrier to access to education.

¹⁷ See best practices and initiatives cited by the MoE, such as teachers4integrations, schools4All, Accelerated Learning Platform for non-linguistic courses etc., available at: <https://migration.gov.gr/en/migration-policy/integration/drasis-koionikis-entaxis-se-ethniko-epipedo/mathimata-ellinikis-glossas/?fbclid=IwAR3CNI-cEalfewpTqjZCMWHUFzOhYz0EH8BTnpHU-6N1JthmXg2SPXHZ8B0>; <https://www.minedu.gov.gr/ekpaideusi/refug-educ>

¹⁸ As from 2020/2021, school enrolment of refugee and migrant-background children raised from 8,637 to 14,423 children out of an estimated 20,000 eligible children. As for the 2021-2022 school year, and according to the data presented by the Minister of Education to the Parliament in February 2022, 26,015 students "born outside Greece, attend Greek elementary and high schools". See also AIDA, 2023 and UNICEF, 2022).

¹⁹ The rate of school attendance was higher for those children living in urban areas, and in apartments provided by UNHCR accommodation scheme as part of the "ESTIA" programme which is no longer running (Emergency Support to Integration and [urban] Accommodation programme, funded by the European Union Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid (ECHO) since 2017-2021), as well as for unaccompanied children in reception camps (66-67% according to UNICEF, 2019). School attendance was especially difficult on the Eastern Aegean islands, when children were obliged to remain for prolonged periods – because of a mandatory geographical restriction that applied to their parents or for UAMs until an accommodation place was found (Council of Europe, 2018).

²⁰ When children cannot prove the legality of their residence, they face difficulties in school enrolment, as an identity document and proof of vaccination booklet are usually requested during enrolment, despite not being a legal requirement.

of movement or arrested, deters parents from approaching public authorities generally, including schools (AIDA, 2023).

When it comes to unaccompanied minors, their situation has significantly improved in the last year. Positive developments include the launching of the National Emergency Response Mechanism (NERM), which operates under the Ministry of Migration and Asylum (MoMA)²¹, in April 2021, and the legislative abolition of ‘protective custody’ (i.e. detention) in 2020. However, UAMs still face challenges due to the lack of an effective guardianship system²². When it comes to education, relevant data statistics²³ show that 8 out of 10 UAMs enrol in schools. However, when it comes to actual attendance, statistics are disheartening. According to focus group discussions by researchers, as well as studies (Anadoxoi Ekpaideytikoi, 2023) 6 out of 10 UAMs leave the shelter before the end of the school year and therefore discontinue education. Out of the remaining 4 in the shelters, only 1 continues school until the end of the school year, whereas 3 leave school eventually for different reasons. Finally, not all of those who stay, manage to get promoted for the next class. Those who do are mostly enrolled at primary school.

Refugee children and especially UAMs are five times more exposed to Early School Leaving (ESL), compared to natives (Greece has one of the lowest share of ESL, 3%, (Psiphidou, 2022, Brown 2021).

4.3 IMMERSE project: evidence-based considerations and critical issues

IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators

IMMERSE (*Integration Mapping of Refugee and Migrant children in Schools and other Experiential environments in Europe*) is a Horizon 2020 project, managed by 11 partners from 6 European countries – Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain. It aimed to map children’s integration in education across a range of indicators identified during the first phase of the project. Integration indicators include factors associated with language and culture, well-being and social connections. Whereas barriers and facilitators identified include those associated with school organisation, mental health services, negative attitudes and learning supports. A key outcome of the research is the development of an interactive dashboard built applying a co-creative methodology that included iterative consultations of children and other relevant stakeholders at different stages. The indicators allow a comparative overview of the degree of integration

²¹ Ministry of Migration and Asylum

²² GCR, Oxfam & Save the Children, Greece: Bimonthly Bulletin on Refugees and Migrants, October 2022, available at: https://www.gcr.gr/media/k2/attachments/GCR_OXFAM_STC_Advocacy_Update_October_2022.pdf, pp. 9-10 and AIDA Report on Greece, 2022 Update, June 2023, available at: https://asylumineurope.org/wpcontent/uploads/2023/06/AIDA-GR_2022-Update.pdf?fbclid=IwAR3wGtKyGiBQLVQVQzmKyGje4IUKwAMdsAGXn5vKwK8BII2JrAuNErWiuxmk, pp. 19-20, 53- 54.

Ans “RECs: The educational integration of refugee children does not fit in closed centres”, 11 May 2023, available at: https://www.efsyn.gr/ellada/dikaiomata/389293_sep-h-ekpaideytiki-entaxiton-prosfygopoylon-den-hora-se-kleista-kentra.

RSA, A Step backwards for protection and integration: On the termination of the ESTIA II housing programme for asylum applicants, 22 December 2022, available at: <https://bit.ly/43vr3Y5>;

For the relevant data see MoMA, Situation Update: Unaccompanied Minors (UAM) in Greece, 1 July 2023, available at: https://migration.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/SSPUAM_Statistics_2023_07_01.pdf.

²³ The most recent ones by ANADOXOI EKPAIDEYTIKOI (surveys on UAMs in shelters, comparing 2018- 2022 school attendance), as well as by GCR, 2023 and AIDA, 2023.

experienced by children in different countries, monitoring its evolution in time and identifying areas of future intervention in a given context²⁴.

Data collection results for Greece

Three thousand two hundred seventy-three surveys were completed in Greece, including 2,336 completed by children of refugee and migrant background, including UAMs²⁵. Out of these, 26,4% were attending primary school, 46,4% secondary school, 3% attended classes but not in regular secondary school, 1,7% declared they were not in any education at the time of the survey. When it comes to country of birth, around 65 countries were recorded, the majority 19% were born in Albania, 16,3% in Afghanistan, 10% in Somalia, 5% in Pakistan, 4,2% in Egypt and 3,7% in Congo. In the last phase of the project, several questionnaires were also completed by children from Ukraine (2,6%). Moreover, researchers collected data from 105 sites of formal education and 42 sites of non-formal education (in NGO premises or UAM shelters, mostly in Athens and Thessaloniki (76%), in 21 towns or suburbs (14%) and in 14 rural areas (10%). Additionally, 3 focus group discussions were held with UAMs and migrant children. Survey data indicated that migrant-background children in Greece expressed high levels of integration across a range of integration indicators: happiness, trust in schools, health services and justice services, but with some concerning trends regarding language, intercultural values at school, bullying, and the variables of age and gender.

Integration outcomes

Language and culture

Refugee and migrant children in Greece reported high and medium levels of competence in Greek (57% high and 32% medium), lower than in other IMMERSE countries (73% high and 21% medium), mainly because of the difficulty of the language. The percentage of high competence is lower in first-generation migrant children as compared to second generation and native children.

More than one-third of migrant-background children in Greece (36%) feel close to both their cultures of origin (parent's country of origin, language, or religion) as well as to other groups of people. This is well below the average (45%) and among the lowest values in IMMERSE countries, besides Italy. In contrast, almost half of them (49%) do not feel close to their cultures of origin, while only 15% feel close to their cultures of origin exclusively. Both percentages are above the average (44% do not feel close to their cultures of origin and 11% only feeling close to people from their culture) and among the highest values in IMMERSE countries, besides Italy.

Well-being

Eighty-four percent of migrant-background children reported being happy or very happy; the second highest across all countries surveyed (81%), together with Ireland (88%). Still 16% report not being happy or not at all happy, in line with the pattern across other IMMERSE countries (average 19%). However, feelings of happiness across participants in Greece differed by age and gender. As

²⁴ The interactive dashboard is in progress. Please visit the following link to discover the indicators: <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/selection-and-creation-of-dashboard-of-socio-educational-integration-indicators/>

²⁵ Among children participants, 41,9% were 1st generation migrant children, 31,2% 2nd generation, and 27% non migrant children. 51,6% children identified themselves as male, 43,9% as female and 1,6% as "in another way". When it comes to their developmental stage at time of survey, 31,7% were in childhood (7-10 years old), 26,4% in early adolescence (11-13 years old), 29,6% in their middle adolescence (14-16 years old) and 11,6% in their late adolescence (17-18 years old). 0,4% were beyond the initial scope of the IMMERSE study (18+) but still attended schools or non formal education.

children grow, the proportion of them reporting happy feelings decreases (starting at 90% for 7 to 9-year-olds and finishing at 77% for 16 to 18-year-olds). Moreover, the participants in Greece that identified their gender in another way reported feeling less happy than their cisnormative peers (71%, versus 29% of male and female).

For those children in Greece enrolled in schools and surveyed, results indicated that 48% of migrant children expressed high levels of belonging in school and another 47% medium level of belonging in school.

On interconnections more than half of the migrant-background children in Greece (58%) declare a high level of support from friends and peers. This is above the average result across IMMERSE countries (54%). Almost sixty percent of migrant and refugee students declare a high support from teachers, being the second higher percentage among IMMERSE (average 57%), along with Spain (68%).

When asked about their degree of trust in teachers and the educational system, 72% of migrant-background older participants in Greece reported high level of trust. This is above the average result across IMMERSE countries (66%).

Data shows that most migrant-background children have a high degree of trust in doctors and hospitals (76%). Police and the justice system were trusted less (64%) and levels of trust are impacted by age with older migrant children being much less trustful of the police/justice system.

Qualitative data from the focus groups emphasised further the importance of friendships and family as sources of securing and belonging to refugee and migrant children. However, along with this was the negotiation of tensions arising out of cultural and religious differences and norms which the young people had to negotiate.

Integration barriers and facilitators

School organisation and teachers

In Greece 51% of school principals²⁶ declared that intercultural values (e.g., appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness, and tolerance) are one of the insignias of their schools and 44% that it is a very important issue, when presenting the schools to parents. Differently, according to teachers' intercultural values are an insignia for less than half (40%) of the sites in Greece, and intercultural values are very important for 57% of them.

According to both principals and teachers, in Greece schools promote parental involvement, however this is not necessarily adapted to parents' specific needs (language, culture, etc). Most schools (65%) do not offer channels allowing for parental involvement adapted for parents' needs.

Considering bullying experiences, 70% of both non migrant and first-generation migrant children reported they have never been bullied. The percentage was 62% for the second generation. Still when in workshops researchers asked, there was a general admittance of children having experienced racism. This might explain why they answered that they avoided places for fear of being treated badly (45% first generation, 40% second generation, 37% non-migrant children).

²⁶ 61 principals completed questionnaires (more than half in relation to the 105 sites) and 68 teachers, which are high and significant numbers but still not representative of the principals and teachers' population in Greece..

Language and Psychosocial Support

According to the survey, the lack of language skills deters migrant-background children from attending school. Although children would prefer enrolment and receiving public school support within formal education, they often receive language support in non-formal education environments (NGOs, shelters, etc), through language support classes (68%) and extracurricular activities (61%). There were no differences in the percentage of children who attend extra-curricular activities by migrant background, with 64% of non-migrant background children attending such activities compared to 66% of first-generation and 57% of second-generation migrant children.

When it comes to full-time or part-time psycho-social or counselling staff, in Greece 71% of the interviewed school principals indicate that they do provide such kind of support in schools (49% part time, 22% fulltime).

Qualitative insights

Researchers in Greece organised focus group discussions with two groups of children from migrant backgrounds, who were participating in non-formal education (with a mix of recently arrived refugee and asylum-seeking children and unaccompanied minors, with an age range between 14 to 17 years old). School experience was discussed, as well as relationships within family, friends, experiences of racism, bullying.

According to the interviewees, school and education create a sense of belonging, provide opportunities for children to make friends, develop language skills and experience 'childhood'. However, UAMs shared their difficulties accessing appropriate education, whereas they have experienced discrimination, and even racism in (and outside) education settings. As main challenges, the difficulties to obtain appropriate legal documents (e.g. residency), and the strict rules of accommodation centres. For UAMs, friends and peers provide a sense of security and belonging. According to those who had experienced school education, they confirmed that school had been central to building these peer relations. The COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on participants in terms of unsatisfactory virtual learning experiences was inescapable with some participants lacking essential requirements and support structures for remote learning, and many speaking of loneliness and loss of interaction with school friends but also family because of restrictions on travel and school attendance.

Good practices

From September 2020 to June 2021, the IMMERSE research partners collected 60 good practices, whose features were reported in a database to facilitate a comparative analysis²⁷. Panteion University identified ten best practices included those initiated from within both the formal and informal education sector and within the community. Almost all (9) targeted newly arrived migrant children and refugee and asylum-seeking children and their families (8). Half (5) included unaccompanied migrant children in their target population while principals, teachers and social workers were targeted by almost all of the initiatives. Most of the best practice projects collected by Greece have multiple objectives aimed at achieving the integration of migrant children (some also include their families). They support both formal and non-formal settings, organise teacher

²⁷ All 60 good practices can be found on IMMERSE's Online Digital Database <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/online-digital-database-of-good-practices-and-resources-in-social-integration-of-refugee-and-migrant-children/>

training activities, handbooks and resources. Most are funded by the EU, or the EEA grants. The importance of involving children, as well as teachers in the education was a main pillar of these activities.

Among the projects identified, there were the Schools for All – Integration of Refugee Children in Greek Schools and the SEDIN Project - Creative Methods for Successful Inclusion in Multicultural Schools. Even if not mentioned in the IMMERSE database, a three-year long UNICEF project started operating during school year 2021-2022, named All Children in Education (ACE). The project aims to facilitate integration of refugee and migrant children in formal education through non-formal education services, such as interpretation services in schools, Greek language courses, and psychosocial support for students.

All three projects (Schools4ALL, ACE and SEDIN) have as a main objective the integration of refugee children in Greek schools through support for teachers, as well as building a safe and inclusive school environment. Most training projects aim to equip school directors and teachers with the tools, competence, and confidence to manage controversy and deal with issues concerning intolerance, discrimination, racism and hate speech in school and the local community. The project Schools4All is implemented under the “Local Development and Poverty Reduction” programme in Greece, by the European Wergeland Centre (EWC), under the auspices of the MoE and Religious Affairs and with the support of the Institute of Educational Policy (IEP). ACE is implemented by UNICEF, the MoE and NGOs. The Erasmus+ project SEDIN was implemented from December 2017 until February 2020 in Greece, among other partners from Bulgaria, Belgium, Italy, Spain, and Turkey. The consortium consisted of NGOs, universities, education and vocational training centres, and state institutions and was based on the idea that mainstream school environments of host countries and the traditional cognitive teaching models are often inadequate to address the needs of children with a migrant background. There is a growing need to introduce in the school environment, in cooperation with different stakeholders, alternative methods that cultivate the fantasy of the children and that promote emotional aspects of learning and positive interaction between migrant children and children belonging to the mainstream communities. SEDIN project developed an e-learning training – an asynchronous online course for teachers including relevant theory as well as practical examples.

A number of other projects coordinated by stakeholders in Greece, especially those working on the protection of children (such as UNICEF, UNHCR, Metadrasi, ARSIS and others) had as a common framework building trust and self-esteem through activities within non formal education which led to the highest number and percentage of refugee and migrant students enrolled and attending schools in 2021/22; and a significant improvement of quality non formal education, as a result of specialised training for staff working with UAMs in vocational orientation and employability guides were organised by MoMA, UNICEF and other experts (Unicef, 2022).

4.4 Policy implications and recommendations

Based on the insights of IMMERSE research activities in Greece, we formulate the following recommendations addressed to policymakers and the education system, to promote a more cohesive and inclusive society for migrant-background children.

We recommend the Government:

- to improve statistics and data collection on education, to make the necessary adjustments in the roll-out of the 2021 census that would allow to capture disadvantaged populations, such as Roma and refugee and migrants, and help inform evidence-based policies. In that respect the Government may foster the collaboration between UNICEF and the National Statistics Office (ELSTAT) in the framework of an existing Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)
- to welcome and implement adequate solutions to the recommendations addressed by the European Commission against Racism and Intolerance (ECRI), which reported that in Greece there is a continuation of racist violence cases against immigrants, refugees and asylum seekers and that hate speech and gender-based violence is particularly widespread on the Internet and in Greece, including against youth.
- to enhance and support new promising practices of synergy among Universities, IOs, Stakeholders and State Authorities.
- to address the obstacles the new asylum application system introduced on 1st September 2022 poses to school enrolment and attendance for children whose parents cannot prove the registration of the asylum claim that they lodge electronically.

We recommend the Ministry of Justice

- to guarantee effective implementation of the 2021 *National Action Plan (NAP) Against Racism* aimed to strengthen educational environments and address bullying in schools and discrimination against LGBT children and migrants.

We recommend the Ministry of Education

- to acknowledge schools as a key institution in the long-term promotion of intercultural values
- to hold information days on the issues of racism and xenophobia, adapted to the respective age groups to which they are addressed.
- to guarantee funding for integration programmes.
- to adopt measures to protect young people, especially in school, from online hate speech.
- to provide funds and sponsor programs for higher education institutions and various organisations in order to conduct surveys on integration and xenophobia issues and to favour cooperation between different stakeholders.

We recommend the Ministry of Migration and Asylum

- to support a special legal status for children having reached adulthood and being left without documents and secure stable and continuous funding.

We recommend the Ministry of Migration and Asylum and the Ministry of Education

- to jointly work to promote the integration of refugee and migrant children through education, promoting good practices of socio-educational in schools and non-formal education setting, involving all relevant stakeholders, such as IOs, UNHCR, UNICEF, IOM, NGOs, Local Authorities, in coordination with the Ministry of Education, to increase the

capacity of schools in urban centres of Athens and Thessaloniki, and provide transportation to and from schools and areas where refugee children and UAMs are living. Furthermore, to issue strict instructions to school directorates that all children must be enrolled, regardless of their residence or legal status, or time of arrival and provide funding for more qualified teachers and increased training in intercultural integration.

We urge the Ministry of Digital Transformation

- to create an effective network for the prevention and effective treatment of hate speech and relevant phenomena with special importance given to the internet.

We recommend school principals

- in case of children that cannot prove the legality of their residence, to facilitate their enrolment until their identity documents and proofs of vaccination are ready.
- to organise training sessions for school bullying as well as inter-cultural values for all (principals, teachers, children, parents) to mainstream relevant policies (see differences in replies by children on school bullying, and principals and teachers on inter-cultural values).
- including parents in the school life should consider and adapt to parents needs and ensure a two-way information sharing (see channels of communication results).
- part-time psychologists should establish trust with children in Schools (one day /week might not be sufficient).

Children’s recommendations for inclusive schools and societies

During policy consultation activities, children formulated recommendations that could improve the socio-educational integration process of migrant-background children. Here are their proposals for an inclusive school and society:

- To develop more fun activities at school (like games, music, athletics, dancing) to strengthen social participation and inclusiveness.
- Teachers should listen and support more migrant-background children.
- To run an information campaign on school enrolment which reaches all refugee and migrant families, as well as school authorities. In this campaign, the government should make clear there are no preconditions related to legal status or residence for enrolment and that knowledge of the Greek language is not a requirement.
- To create a special legal status for children having reached adulthood and being left without documents.
- Children’s voices should be taken into account in co-creating policies that affect their future. For example, youth committees can take part in initiatives of MoMA and the SSPUAM²⁸, with the support of NGOs working in the field.

²⁸ See for example the National Emergency Response Mechanism: A safety net for unaccompanied children identified in precarious living conditions (NERM) which runs a 24/7 tracing line for identifying children in need and providing guidance to children, citizens, local and public authorities on supporting UAC; finds placements for UAC in special emergency accommodation facilities; provides material and psychosocial support, interpretation services and guidance with official registration procedures; follows Standard Operational Procedures (SOPs) and conducts a Best Interest Assessment (BIA) for all UAC; ensures proper registration and protection of unaccompanied and separated children from Ukraine

4.5 Conclusions

The IMMERSE Project has proved to be essential in documenting the reality faced by refugee and migrant children in schools and non-formal educational settings in Greece. The dashboard of indicators, the data collection survey, the qualitative activities, with the direct participation of children, revealed the existence of good integration results, as well as numerous shortcomings, some evident, others difficult to detect, such as how we can reconcile the trust children show to their teachers with high school dropout rates for high school refugee children and UAMs. The data show the importance of synergies among relevant ministries, the need to connect housing benefits and educational realities in school enrolment, and the importance of streamlining migration policies with a view to achieving quality education for all. Moreover, it is fundamental to have targeted National Action Plans (NAPs) (not only for UAMs but for all refugee and migrant children; favour the coordination among NGOs and other IOs efforts at municipal and regional level; and guarantee funds to support long term projects. Recent initiatives and legislative changes have improved the situation of some groups of migrant children, such as UAMs, but specific actions are required to improve holistic integration.

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arriving in Greece (such as BIA assessments at borders); coordinates information desks in Athens and Thessaloniki. <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/system/files/2023-03/NERM%20Procedural%20Handbook.pdf>

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5 National recommendation paper – Ireland: IMMERSE Results and Policy Considerations in the Irish Context

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5.1 Executive summary

This paper offers an overview of policy orientation on the integration of migrants and refugees in Ireland with a specific focus on migrant children and youth in education. Results from the Irish IMMERSE quantitative and qualitative research are detailed, alerting us to ongoing issues to be addressed in order to foster and deepen belonging and integration. Key concerns, particularly regarding deteriorating levels of happiness and belonging and their intersection with age and gender are highlighted. The importance of adaptation of participation channels to migrant contexts in order to enable meaningful participation is emphasised as is the strength of cross sector cooperation and dialogue.

5.2 The Irish context

The 2016 Census figures show that a total of 96,497 migrant students were enrolled in primary and second level education in Ireland (CSO, 2017). According to the most recent census, migrants originating outside the EU and UK account for 13.8% of Ireland’s population (CSO, 2022) and it is estimated that over 10% of migrants are aged between 0-14 (ibid). All migrant children have access to preschool, primary and secondary education, similar to non-migrant children and compulsory education is up to 16, in practice young people remain in education up to the end of secondary school, commonly to age 18/19.

Considering the integration process, one key issue identified by the Interdepartmental Working Group on the Integration of Refugees in Ireland, in *Integration - A two way process* (1998), relates to language. Further issues identified within this report included perceptions of migrants as a dependent population whose positive contributions to society were, largely, not appreciated; low levels of encounters between host community and migrants, and verbal and to a lesser extent, physical, racism.

From 1998 – 2008, the National Consultative Committee on Racism and Interculturalism (NCCRI) engaged in educational and awareness campaigns challenging dominant stereotypes on migrants and minority ethnic groups. In the meantime, *Planning for Diversity - The National Action Plan Against Racism (2005 - 2008)*, was developed. Its stated aim was ‘to provide strategic direction to combat racism and to develop a more inclusive, intercultural society in Ireland based on a commitment to inclusion by design, not as an add-on or afterthought and based on policies that promote interaction, equality of opportunity, understanding and respect’ (p.27). Following a consultation process in 2021 a further NAP is now in development.

With regard to education, NAP planned the development of an intercultural educational strategy, the development of inclusive and intercultural practice within schools and accommodation of diversity within the school curricula. It proposed enhanced participation of refugees and asylum seeker children in school and highlighted the need for a specific focus on females. These aims were reiterated in Ireland's *Intercultural Education Strategy 2010-2015* (2010), developed by the Departments of Education and Skills and the Office of the Minister for Integration. Its key aim was to ensure respect for diversity in a spirit of partnership and ensuring support for educational providers in normalising inclusion and integration within schools.

Support in the form of additional specialised teaching staff is available to schools who have high numbers of migrant students whose first language is not English. While this is a welcome support for children's learning and participation, sufficient levels of resourcing remain problematic. An intercultural Language Support Toolkit was developed by the European Centre for Modern Languages (ECML), including advice and resources to address language and cultural diversity in school²⁹, adding to language support available to schools in Ireland.

Supports for disadvantaged students whereby schools targeted through the Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS) programme, are allocated a package of resources. This programme was developed in 2005 to address socio-economic disadvantage and its scope was extended, in 2017, to incorporate further factors, including children from minority ethnic groups and those living in Ireland's International Protection System (Department of Education, 2022). While its expanded scope is welcome, it only partially speaks to more specific issues arising for the wider cohort of migrant students.

5.3 Immerse project: evidence-based considerations and critical issues

Results of the IMMERSE Irish survey

IMMERSE (*Integration Mapping of Refugee and Migrant children in Schools and other Experiential environments in Europe*) is a Horizon 2020 project, managed by 11 partners from 6 European countries – Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain. It aimed to map children's integration in education across a range of indicators identified during the first phase of the project. Integration indicators include factors associated with language and culture, well-being and social connections. Whereas barriers and facilitators identified include those associated with school organisation, mental health services, negative attitudes and learning supports. A key outcome of the research is the development of an interactive dashboard whereby issues identified by the diverse research strands can be analysed and visually disaggregated. This accessible and interactive tool will further the publicly accessible information and understanding of issues concerning and impacting on migrant children across Europe³⁰.

One thousand five hundred surveys were completed in Ireland, including 830 completed by children of migrant background. Additionally, 3 focus group discussions were held with a) minority ethnic children of Roma origin (2) and b) unaccompanied migrant children (1). Survey data indicated that migrant children in Ireland expressed high levels of integration across a range of integration

²⁹ Available at this link: <https://ilaos.ppli.ie/the-toolkit/>

³⁰ Follow this link to IMMERSE indicators: <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/selection-and-creation-of-dashboard-of-socio-educational-integration-indicators/>

indicators: happiness, trust in schools, health services and justice services, but with some concerning trends regarding age and gender.

Eighty-eight percent of migrant-background children in Ireland who completed surveys reported being happy or very happy; the highest across all IMMERSE countries where on average, 81% of migrant children reported being happy or very happy. However, it was found that in Ireland, Italy and Spain, migrant girls were slightly less likely to be happy than boys and concerningly, those who defined their gender 'in another way' were 3 to 6 times more likely to report being unhappy.

According to Irish survey results, police and the justice system were trusted by a large majority (70%), which was the highest level of trust across IMMERSE countries where on average, 62% of migrant children reported they trusted the justice system. However, again levels of trust are impacted by age, with older migrant children being much less trustful of the justice system. These factors raise concerns in Ireland in how gender and age intersect with migrant status. Furthermore, our qualitative research indicates low levels of trust in the justice system, as well as frequent experiences of discrimination, negative stereotyping and racist profiling of ethnic minority youth.

Survey data indicated that 47% of migrant children reported being bullied and 48% avoided particular places. Both of these figures are above an average of 38% and 40% respectively, for these indicators across partner countries.

Qualitative data indicated the importance of friendships and family as sources of securing and belonging to migrant children. However, along with this was the negotiation of tensions arising out of cultural and religious differences and norms which the young people had to negotiate.

The importance of schools as sites of integration and belonging was also raised in survey and qualitative research undertaken. In Ireland 143 principals and 25 teachers completed surveys. Results from this data, while not necessarily representative of the context across all schools in Ireland, indicated that over half of these schools do not have psycho-social supports or personal counselling staff. There were diverging perspectives on the importance of intercultural values within the ethos of schools with principals reporting far greater emphasis on these values (67%) than teachers (40%). A further associated barrier to integration identified through these surveys, was poor adaptation of parental engagement channels for migrant parents in Ireland, despite the availability of several parental engagement channels. The latter included information on children's progress, opportunities to volunteer and avenues to participate in decision-making. Children reported that school places could sometimes be difficult to identify, an issue that was raised in our qualitative research. Some children reported having to wait months before finding a school place, as expressed by this young focus group participant. 'I come to Limerick, but I don't find the school and after two months I come to Dublin with my family'.

Good practices

IMMERSE project carried out an analysis of 60 good practices at local, national and European level. Identification and analysis of these ensures the availability of detail of the origins, motivations, work and development of innovative and diverse integration pathways for migrant children across Europe. Following their compilation, a dedicated online searchable resource is available for those

working to promote migration integration pathways³¹. In Ireland also, 2 webinars were organised in November 2021 and February 2022, in order to further disseminate knowledge on the Irish good practices and facilitate intra-initiative discussions.

Ireland's ten best practices included those initiated from within the formal education sector and within the community. Almost all (9) targeted newly arrived migrant children and refugee and asylum-seeking children and their families (8). Half (5) included unaccompanied migrant children in their target population while principals, teachers and social workers were targeted by 8 of the initiatives. One mentioned victims of human trafficking as being specifically targeted by them for support.

Most of these have multiple objectives aimed at achieving the holistic integration of migrant children and their families through supporting their formal educational participation and creating opportunities for wider informal educational activities, for instance through drama, dancing, multi-media and art, aimed at increasing their educational exposure and their confidence in their abilities. One was solely aimed at influencing policy internationally, spanning the Irish and EU context. This orientation reflected that of the full set of best practices of which 95% addressed multiple targets. A key message arising from such alignment is an understanding that migrant children's integration in education necessarily encompasses children, their families and communities and that the support of professionals outside of teaching roles is an important factor in supporting integration. A related issue is the nature of the school year, which is bound by term times and year transitions in the education sector.

Such understanding was evident through the involvement of a wide range of professionals in the Irish best practices. A wide range of professionals supported all of the examples identified, including educators and academics (10), teachers (8), psychologists and cultural mediators (6) and legal experts (3). Initiatives were also supported by other professionals, including sports coaches, artists, youth leaders as well those representing statutory and regional organisations.

All best practices involved non-governmental organisations and universities while 7 involved schools. Eight examples incorporated parent and student associations, reflecting the importance of family and community involvement and cross-community understanding whereas government and regional authorities were involved in 5 initiatives. While support at national and international levels is important, the involvement of more localised institutions ensures that such support is actioned on the ground, highlighting the significance of diversity of involvement, which was identified across all 60 best practices gathered.

8 initiatives included extra-curricular activities while language support was an element of 7, reflecting a common thread across those collected in all 6 countries where just over 40% included language classes and 55% incorporated/focused upon extra-curricular activities for the children. Vocational training was included in 4 of the best practices and other elements of the initiatives included dance, drama, art, sports, IT training, cultural awareness and anti-racist training, maintaining cultural identity while adopting cultural competencies. These initiatives highlight the importance of further and more informal education and their role in supporting integration. They also bring attention to the importance of developing and sustaining networks of association as well

³¹ All 60 good practices can be found in IMMERSE's Online Digital Database <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/online-digital-database-of-good-practices-and-resources-in-social-integration-of-refugee-and-migrant-children/>

as providing opportunities to engage in new skills; all of which support sustainable integration. Such was recognised across the consortium where one third of initiatives identified were aimed at creating and encouraging networks and exchanging good practices of inclusion. Encouraging and enabling feelings of belonging and enhancing self-esteem, happiness, supporting engagement with friends and peers, academic skills and completion of compulsory education were indicators identified by 8 of the best practices, closely followed by supporting competence in children's mother tongue (7) and enabling of participation in non-compulsory formal and informal education (6). All ten best practices identified educational achievements and increased connectedness as expected outcomes while 9 named language and culture and wellbeing.

All were involved in some way in disseminating information on their work, through the production of toolkits, internal evaluations and production of project reports for funders, as well as dissemination in practice and academic journals.

Short term and/or sector specific funding was an issue that was identified as being a barrier to the ongoing work. Those initiatives that had origins in community organisations tended to rely on ad hoc funding sources or they were funded for specific periods through UN Resettlement programmes. However, cognisant that integration support extended beyond the allocated time period they sought further funding to sustain supports initiated. This was possible through the networks of association developed, but simultaneously placed the supports on precarious foundations, with ongoing development uncertain.

5.4 Policy implications and recommendations

Based on the insights of IMMERSE research activities in Ireland, we formulate the following recommendations addressed to policymakers and the education system, to promote a more cohesive and inclusive society for migrant-background children.

Recommendations for School and Education Support for Integration

- Increased support by the Department of Education for teachers' acquisition of intercultural competencies, strengthening intercultural education in their initial and in-service training.
- Promotion of extracurricular and support activities at school and outside school to increase children's opportunities to develop peer relations, thus combating social exclusion and isolation. These supports could be organised by regional Educational Training Boards (ETB).
- Development of counselling and psycho-social supports across schools in Ireland by the Department of Education, in cooperation with the Department of Children, Disability, Integration and Youth. Such supports would contribute to enabling migrant children to fully participate in education as well as enhancing their belonging and deepening educational understanding of issues of concern to them.
- Recognising and addressing racism in schools necessitates acknowledging and challenging racist attitudes and the enactment of biases, from micro-aggressions through to physical violence among peers. Development of Anti-Racism Continuing Professional Development (CPD) modules, with resource support from the Department of Education to contribute to furthering the key aim of the *Intercultural Educational Strategy 2015*, in normalising inclusion and integration within schools.

Recommendations for Teacher Training/Resource Supports

- Increased provision of training for Special Education Needs (SEN) and Language Support, particularly support for competence in English as an Additional Language (EAL) through increased funding allocations of the Department of Education.
- Increase of funding for CPD language support by the Department of Education, and the recognition of these by Education Support Centres regionally, including teacher training in immersive, inclusive and innovative teaching techniques.
- There needs to be greater recognition of and support for children's linguistic diversity within schools and increased opportunities to retain home languages. To this end, it is important that the Department of Education and the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment expands language choice for non-European languages to i) promote language choice options in the curricula and ii) as exam subjects.

Recommendations for Community, Political and Societal Supports for Integration

- Ongoing support for school/community initiatives, supported by relevant government departments, that extend beyond the school year, including school holidays, to support holistic integration of migrant children and their families. For example, development of targeted supports to allow migrant children access local extra-curricular activities. Relevant Departments include the Department of Education, Department of Rural and Community Development, Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth, Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, Department of Heritage and Local Government, Department of Health.
- Engagement of schools with local authorities, police and non-governmental organisations to identify potentially dangerous areas where migrant-background children may be targets of discriminatory and bullying actions, to contribute to ensuring children's safety in their journeys to and from school.
- Ensuring cross sector initiatives are robustly supported necessarily involves cross Government Department co-operation as well as the allocation of specific responsibility for driving this co-operation within one Government Department. We recommend cross-department cooperation across all relevant departments, including but not confined to, the Department of Education, Department of Rural and Community Development, Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth, Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, Department of Heritage and Local Government, Department of Health.
- The development of long-term cross-sector and process-oriented funding avenues to enable, support and develop dialogue, discussion and initiatives across education and community sectors. This entails the cooperation of government departments including but not confined to the Department of Education, Department of Rural and Community Development, Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth, Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, Department of Heritage and Local Government, Department of Health.

- Dedicated resourcing of schools by the Department of Education in conjunction with the Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth and the Department of Justice, to develop more proactive work in schools, communities and with the gardaí.

Recommendations for Local Authorities

- Dedicated resourcing of Local Authority Social Inclusion Units and TUSLA - The Child and Family Agency's, Children and Young People Services Committees, to concentrate on locally driven educational integration initiatives targeting migrant children and youth.

Children's recommendations for inclusive schools and societies

- More proactive engagement with addressing racism and bullying with a particular focus on bullying aimed at LGBTQI+ and non-binary students.
- Engagement of schools with local communities and the police to foster greater understanding and trust across sectors.
- Younger children recommended less focus on homework and more on listening to them.

5.5 Conclusions

IMMERSE survey results in Ireland demonstrate that migrant-background children feel high levels of belonging, trust teachers, and receive support from friends and peers, with differences based on age and gender. Nevertheless, qualitative findings indicate that migrant and ethnic youth commonly experience bullying, racism and ethnic stereotyping. Thus, it is urgent to address racism within educational settings and across communities, in the pursuit of greater levels of belonging.

Identification and analysis of good practices reveal broad ranging and innovative initiatives aimed at broadening and deepening educational opportunities and cross-cultural understanding. However, they also reveal a need to consider and support connections between school, family, community and neighbourhoods in ensuring full and free participation of migrant children and youth in education.

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6 National recommendations paper – Italy: The socio-educational integration of migrant-background children in Italy: evidence and policy proposals from the IMMERSE project

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6.1 Executive summary

The present policy paper summarises and discusses the main results of the IMMERSE research project, with a specific focus on the work undertaken in Italy. The aim is to provide innovative data and recommendations about the socio-educational integration of migrant-background children in schools and other educational environments in the country. In the first part, a brief overview of the Italian migration and integration context will be offered through official data and a brief literature review, along with a mention of the national socio-educational integration policies for refugee and migrant minors. The second part introduces the IMMERSE H2020 project and analyses the research results, stressing critical issues to address and good practices to consider for a better common model of integration. Finally, the last section informs policymakers and the educational sector with specific recommendations.

6.2 The Italian context

In the last decades, Italy has been highly engaged with migration flows, with consequences on the school system especially. Since the school year 1983/84, the country has experienced a perpetual increase in the number of students with a migration background (MIM, Aug. 2023)³². In the school year 2021/22³³, there were 872,360 students without Italian citizenship: 10.6% of all students enrolled in kindergartens, primary and secondary schools³⁴. They come from more than 200 countries³⁵, but 67.5% were born in Italy³⁶ (ibid.). Recently, with the outbreak of the Russian-

³² Except for the s.y. 2020/21, when the total number of students decreased, probably due to Covid-19 pandemics on kindergarten attendance.

³³ The Ministry of Education and Merit provides periodic disaggregated data about students based on the citizenship status. However, these official numbers do not include other profiles of migrant children and adolescents, such as refugee, asylum-seeking, or unaccompanied minors.

³⁴ The Italian school system has three levels of education according to age (kindergarten aged 3-6, primary school aged 6-11, I-level secondary school aged 11-13, and II-level secondary school aged 13-18). Students without Italian citizenship represent 11.7% of all students at kindergarten, 12.4% in primary school, 11.2% in I-level secondary school, and 8% in II-level secondary school. 65.5% of students without Italian citizenship attend schools located in the Northern regions, 21.9% in the Central regions and 12.6% in the Southern regions and in the Islands (MIM, Aug. 2023).

³⁵ 44.1% of students without Italian citizenship come from Europe, 27.56% from Africa, 20.52% from Asia (MIM, Aug. 2023).

³⁶ From the s.y. 2017/18 to the s.y. 2021/22, the number of children without Italian citizenship but born on the Italian territory went from 531,467 to 588,986, with an increase of more than 57,000 units (+10.8%). In primary schools, almost three out of four foreign students were born in Italy (73.6%); in I-level secondary schools the percentage is 67% and in II level secondary schools it is 48.3% (MIM, Aug. 2023).

Ukrainian war, Italy welcomed 27,506 Ukrainian students from February to June 2022 (MI, 13/06/2022). Moreover, Italy hosts 21,710 unaccompanied migrant minors (UAMs), mostly aged 16 or 17 and coming from Egypt, Ukraine, Tunisia, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Gambia, and Albania³⁷.

In this scenario, the Italian school system has been particularly engaged with the challenge of integration and interculturality. Despite the commitment of schools and many local good practices, the scarcity and inadequacy of organisational, economic, and professional resources limit the efficacy of interventions (Osservatorio nazionale per l'integrazione degli alunni stranieri e per l'intercultura/MIUR, 2020). Most migrant-background children have fewer opportunities than their classmates. Differences are evident when considering the attendance level at kindergartens³⁸, school drop-out rates and grade repetition, as well as emerging segregation phenomena such as the *white flight*, i.e. the choice of Italian families to enrol their children in central urban areas, thus increasing the concentration of foreign students in suburban schools (Pacchi and Ranci, 2017).

In the school year 2021/22, while 8.1% Italian students were off-track with their education, the figure for non-Italian students reached 25.4% (MIM, Aug. 2023). According to INVALSI³⁹ data, at the end of the first cycle of education, the percentage of first-generation immigrants that do not reach the minimum levels of competences in Italian, Maths and English is double (26%) that of the percentage of Italian students or second-generation students (INVALSI, 2023). Moreover, in 2022 the percentage of Early School Leavers⁴⁰ was three times higher among migrant-background youth born abroad (30.1%), compared to those born in Italy but without the Italian citizenship (9.8%) (Istat, 2023). Another alarming fact concerns NEETs⁴¹: the percentage is significantly higher among foreign adolescents and young adults, (28.8%) compared to Italians (18%) (ibid.).

In general, scholastic achievement and integration at school are weakened by linguistic barriers, the fact that migrant-background students are often enrolled in classes not corresponding to their age⁴², and the absence/insufficiency of cultural mediation services, which affect student learning and school performance, as well as family participation (Santagati and Colussi, 2022). Moreover, the concentration of migrant-background children in specific schools and classes complicates the process of integration⁴³. Studies show that, especially in primary schools, less experienced and

³⁷ Data refers up to 31st July 2023. The dataset is available at: <https://analytics.lavoro.gov.it/t/PublicSIM/views/PresenzadeiMinoriStranierinonaccompanatiinItalia/PresenzadeiMinoriStranierinonaccompanatiinItalia?%3Aembed=y&%3Aiid=3&%3AisGuestRedirectFromVizportal=y> [Accessed 15 Sept. 2023]. Their rights are established in the Consolidated Act on immigration (Legislative decree n. 286/1998) and the following implementation act (Presidential Decree 394/1999). Moreover, Italy is the only European country that adopted a specific law for the protection of UAMs (Law n. 47/2017). This law and the "Guidelines for the right to education of minors outside their family of origin" (2017) reiterate UAMs' right to education.

³⁸ While 95.1% of Italian children aged 3 to 5 attend kindergarten, only 77.9% of children without Italian citizenship do (MIM, Aug. 2023).

³⁹ INVALSI is the National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System in Italy.

⁴⁰ Those aged 18-24 who abandon their studies or training courses prematurely, without obtaining a high-school diploma.

⁴¹ Not in Education, Employment or Training.

⁴² Although the Italian law requires enrolment in classes corresponding to child age, except in case of a different evaluation by the school board. See the provisions of the Consolidated Act on Immigration (Legislative Decree no. 286/1998), the Ministerial note no. 101 of 8 January 2010, the indications contained in the annual ministerial circulars on registrations and the Guidelines for intercultural orientation (2022).

⁴³ According to the provisions of the Ministry of Education (C.M. n. 2, 8 January 2010, Indications and recommendations for the integration of pupils with non-Italian citizenship), there is a maximum threshold of 30% of pupils with non-Italian citizenship in classes and schools. However, there are upward or downward exemptions, defined together with the Regional School Offices, based on student Italian language skills. In Italy, only 18% of schools are entirely made up of students with Italian citizenship. The majority of schools (74.8%) have a presence of foreign students lower than 30%,

less motivated teachers are assigned to classes with a higher number of students with a migration background (Santagati and Colussi, 2022). The lack/scarcity of school services and extra-curricular, cultural, and social activities, especially in the most disadvantaged areas at risk of educational poverty (Save the Children Italy, 2022a), further limits opportunities for social interactions and cultural contamination. Additionally, economic poverty weighs on children's learning paths, especially among foreign families⁴⁴. The pandemic aggravated even further children's education and integration path, interrupting language courses, learning processes, and extra-curricular activities⁴⁵.

Interestingly, citizenship also determines children's school performance, opportunities, study motivation, social relations, and future prospects (Gathmann et al., 202; Avitabile et al., 2014; Felfe et al., 2016; Save the Children Italy, 2023). In Italy, the current law on citizenship (Law n. 91/1992) recognizes the *ius sanguinis* principle and establishes strict criteria for acquiring the status of Italian citizenship⁴⁶, consequently limiting the rights and opportunities of migrant children born or growing up in Italy, both at school and outside school.

The Italian Constitution requires schools to be open to everyone⁴⁷, in line with arts. 29 and 30 of the CRC. According to the Presidential Decree 394/1999, children have the right to access education, independently of their migration background, legal or administrative status (or those of their parents).

The National observatory for the integration of foreign students and intercultural published guidance documents to define integration principles and interventions for the creation of an Italian multicultural school model⁴⁸. Moreover, in March 2022 the Ministry of Education and Merit disclosed guidelines for intercultural orientation (Osservatorio nazionale per l'integrazione degli alunni stranieri e per l'interculturalità/MIUR, 2022), underlining in the preamble how sociocultural pluralism in schools and communities represents both a challenge and a great opportunity to rethink the school system and its mandate.

6.3 The IMMERSE project: evidence-based considerations and critical issues

IMMERSE (*Integration Mapping of Refugee and Migrant children in Schools and other Experiential environments in Europe*) is a Horizon 2020 project, managed by 11 partners from 6 European countries – Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Spain⁴⁹. In the following sections, we

while 7.2% have 30% or a higher percentage of foreign students. The number of classes with more than 30% of foreign students has been increasing in recent years (6,8% in s.y. 2021/22, 6,6% in s.y. 2020/21, 6,1% in s.y. 2019/20, 5,9% in s.y. 2018/19, 5,6% in s.y. 2017/18, 5,3% in s.y. 2016/17) (MIM, Aug. 2023).

⁴⁴ In 2021 families in absolute poverty with only foreign members were 36.2%; mixed families were 30.7%; while families with only Italian members were 8.3% (Istat, 15/06/2022).

⁴⁵ The pandemic also highlighted the socio-economic deprivation of many children who do not have technological devices, stable Internet connections or suitable spaces for learning (Save the Children Italy, 2021).

⁴⁶ Migrant-background children can basically acquire Italian citizenship when they turn 18 by submitting a statement of intent or once their parents obtain citizenship after 10 years of uninterrupted residence on the national territory.

⁴⁷ Art. 34 Italian Constitution

⁴⁸ For more information, see MIUR (2006) and Osservatorio nazionale per l'integrazione degli alunni stranieri e per l'interculturalità/MIUR (2020, 2015 and 2007),

⁴⁹ For more info, visit <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/it/>

discuss the project's main activities and results which led to the formulation of policy recommendations addressed to policymakers and the educational system.

IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators

At European and national level there are existing data sources that establish sets of socio-educative indicators, examining different aspects of integration, but without a common approach. Examples are the Zaragoza indicators, the OECD socio-economic indicators, the PISA socio-educational indicators, and the Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX). Most frameworks lack a child-centred perspective, applying only to the adult population, and have a limited scope that overlooks, for instance, the ecological factors that influence children growth over time (Bajo Marcos et al., 2023). In Italy, the Ministry of Education and Merit provides periodic disaggregated data about students based on the citizenship status, excluding other profiles of migrant children and adolescents, such as refugee, asylum-seeking, or unaccompanied minors.

In this context, the main contribution of IMMERSE has been to define, from a whole school approach, a brand-new set of indicators (IMMERSE Dashboard) to study the state of the art of the socio-educational integration of migrant-background minors in schools in Italy and Europe, identifying barriers and facilitators that influence the process and determine the creation of more cohesive and inclusive societies.

Through a co-creation method that encompassed dialogue with many relevant stakeholders and listening to and participation of children and adolescents, IMMERSE partners developed a *dashboard* of 30 integration indicators, divided into 14 *outcomes* and 16 *determinants*, in order to capture relevant variables that influence the path and experience of inclusion at the micro (minors and their families), meso (educational centres, educational communities and neighbourhoods) and macro levels (society and institutions). The results of integration (outcomes) are divided into five dimensions: access to rights, language and culture, wellbeing, social connection, and educational achievement. The barriers and factors facilitating integration (determinants) are instead linked to the areas: leadership politics, school segregation, learning support, mental health services, negative attitudes, school organisation and teachers⁵⁰.

This set of indicators allows a comparative overview of the degree of integration experienced by children in different countries, monitoring its evolution over time and identifying areas of future intervention in a given context.

Data collection results for Italy⁵¹

In Italy, the quantitative survey involved 8,053 students⁵². Around 58% were non-migrant children, 28% second-generation migrant, and 14% first-generation migrant.

⁵⁰ The dashboard indicators are available at this link: <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/selection-and-creation-of-dashboard-of-socio-educational-integration-indicators/>

⁵¹ Results are based on data received and analysed by 30th June 2023.

⁵² 84.6% are older children (OC; aged 10-17), and 15.4% younger children (YC, aged 7-9). Most children attend secondary school (92.2%), while fewer interviewees attend primary school (6%). Only 1.5% of students affirm that they take courses, but not in a regular secondary school, while only 0.3% are not in any kind of education. Questionnaires were administered in both formal and non-formal education sites (73.2% and 26.8%, respectively).

Concerning the dimension of *language and culture*, the majority of migrant-background children in Italy (76%) declare a high competence in Italian. However, 1 out of 4 students (24%) declare a low or medium competence, especially among first-generation migrant children.

Over half of migrant-background children in Italy (52%)⁵³ do not feel close to their cultures of origin. The percentage is slightly higher among second-generation (55%), born and grown up in Italy, compared to first-generation children (48%). Nearly one-third of migrant-background children (35%), instead, feel close to both their cultures of origin as well as to other groups of people (e.g. Italians, people living in the same city, peers, etc.), a feeling that increases by age. Although this is a sign of the opportunity for children in Italy to maintain their cultural identity while adopting a new one, this data is below the average (45%) and the lowest value in IMMERSE countries. Nevertheless, a small proportion (13%), especially among first-generation children, feel close to their cultures of origin exclusively, which may suggest difficulties in the integration process.

In terms of child *wellbeing*, the data regarding the sense of belonging in their schools reveals a general disaffection towards the Italian school system, with only around 2 out of 5 migrant-background students feeling a high sense of belonging (37% second generation migrant children; 39% first generation migrant children); non-migrant background peers share a similar feeling (40%). Interestingly, the percentage of migrant-background children feeling a high sense of belonging in their schools (37%) is notably lower than in other IMMERSE countries (average 48%). This feeling dramatically diminishes as they grow: from 67% of small children down to 32% among early adolescents and 23% among middle adolescents. In Italy, migrant-background children are slightly less happy (79%) than native children (83%) and compared to other IMMERSE countries (e.g. Ireland 88%; Greece 84%). One out of 5 children feels not very or not at all happy, a negative condition that notably increases with age (from 11% of small children, to 19% of early adolescents, 28% of middle adolescents and 27% of late adolescents).

Analysing the domain of *social connections*, data show that only 41% of migrant-background children declare a high level of support from friends and peers and 47% receive a high level of support from teachers, data that are well below the average and the lowest results across IMMERSE countries⁵⁴ (average: 54% and 58%, respectively). Teachers seem to become less supportive as children grow: the percentage of migrant-background children that perceive high support notably diminishes from 69% of small children, to 46% of early adolescents, and further to 35-38% among middle and late adolescents. Teachers and schools are trusted by almost two-thirds of migrant-background children (63%), although the percentage dramatically diminishes with age: from 91% of small children, to 65% of early adolescents, and further to 48-47% among middle and late adolescents. 15% of children with a migration background declare clear distrust. This aspect recalls the centrality of the role of teachers in promoting social inclusion and the importance of their initial and in-service education and training (European Commission, 2017).

Additionally, IMMERSE data show that 2 out of 5 migrant-background children in Italy do not attend language or learning support activities (40%), or other extra-curricular activities (42%), either at school or in their neighbourhood. Simultaneously, the percentage of those who take part in these

⁵³ i.e. parent's country of origin, language, or religion.

⁵⁴ Data about support from friends and peers and support from teachers shows very small differences between migrant and non-migrant children.

activities notably diminishes with age, suggesting the limited availability, inadequacy of or lack of knowledge about these learning support activities.

Finally, over one third of the migrant-background children in Italy (39%) have been bullied at some point and 42% avoid places for fear of being badly treated, which is similar to non-migrant background children (37% and 39%, respectively) but slightly above the average across IMMERSE countries (38% and 40%, respectively).

Qualitative insights

IMMERSE research also provided some qualitative insights⁵⁵ to explore the path of inclusion and examine the most important challenges and opportunities that migrant minors experience in Italy. Interviews with migrant-background children – including "new generation" children (i.e. second generation) and UAMs, their families, practitioners, teachers, experts, and policymakers, revealed how legal and citizenship status can influence migrant-background children's vulnerability, access to education and social participation. Not holding Italian citizenship is indeed a key factor, which reduces migrant-background children's sense of belonging and desire to participate in community social life (Istat, 2020; Save the Children Italy, 2023).

Moreover, some critical issues distinguish the school and training paths of young people of foreign origin compared to their native peers, such as, for example, linguistic barriers, delays in access to education, enrolment in classes not corresponding to their age, risk of drop-out and difficulty in peer-to-peer relationships due to prejudice and stigmatisation. Specifically, linguistic barriers are related to the limited implementation of L2 courses – which are also heterogeneously distributed across territories –, migrant-background children's low attendance rate of kindergarten, as well as the absence of effective plurilingual contexts and practices.

In many cases, the adolescents who were interviewed highlighted the absence of an inclusive school climate. Additionally, unavailable psycho-social support services further expose migrant-background children to psychological vulnerability and limit their wellbeing.

Additionally, in line with other research studies (Azzolini, 2011; Romito, 2014; Aktas et al., 2021; Bonizzoni et al., 2016; Santagati and Colussi, 2022), results show that stereotyped and discriminatory representations affect student-teacher relationships and the career guidance advice for students with migration backgrounds.

Regarding UAMs, it is difficult to frame an effective integration process due to their often-short stay and the inadequate educational opportunities offered by the territory. They often access education once the school year has already started. Moreover, they are extensively enrolled in centres for the education of adults (CPIA), rather than the ordinary school system, reducing their chances to socialise with peers⁵⁶.

⁵⁵ See IMMERSE (2020) and IMMERSE (2022b).

⁵⁶ UAMs can access formal education systems, but the linguistic barriers and the non-recognition of their school certificates lead to their frequent enrolment in vocational training and non-formal education, such as Centres for the Education of Adults (CPIA). CPIA offer tailor-made training paths, however limiting social interaction opportunities with same-age peers (Save the Children Italy, 2022). Moreover, studies highlight that the quality of education interventions for UAMs is weakened by their temporary presence in a territory/in a school, the complexity of bureaucratic procedures, a rigid learning offer, the difficulties accessing school during the school year, the lack of adequate learning resources, the

The collected interviews revealed the difficulties of the Italian school system which seems to inadequately manage the integration process due to limited economic resources for support, and linguistic and extra-curricular activities, as well as fragmented intercultural approaches and inadequately trained teachers. Consequently, families, legal guardians and educators in non-formal education centres play a key role in supporting the learning path of migrant-background children.

The qualitative interviews further stressed the fragmentation of social, housing, sanitary and education services, which exacerbates deprivation and inequalities.

Good practices

Partners identified 60 good practices aiming at inclusive education and social innovation at local, national or EU level, to stimulate ideas and projects for a common model of integration and a more welcoming school for minors with a migration background⁵⁷. Most case studies aim to guarantee migrant and refugee children's access and completion of formal education, improve children's academic skills and language competences, as well as enhance the relationships with peers, teachers, and institutions. Nearly all of them seek to increase children's sense of belonging and many promote innovation at school through new inclusive approaches, governance models and teaching methods that enhance intercultural education by placing the child, his/her story and identity at the centre. Most projects balance common needs and specific needs, guaranteeing equal but flexible interventions.

Initiatives propose multiple school and extra-curricular activities, aimed not only at minors of migrant origin, but also families, school staff, and the wider community.

The mapped good practices adopt a multi-stakeholder, interdisciplinary approach that includes the collaboration of various professionals with different expertise (pedagogy, education, psychology, cultural mediation, health, law, research, etc.) and heterogeneous networks, involving government and local authorities, NGOs, school communities, universities, and research centres.

Almost all initiatives disseminate their results and methodologies through various communication channels. As a result, most of them have been scaled up or have the potential to be transferred to similar or different contexts.

Projects receive European, governmental, or private funds, which are fundamental to incentivize effective actions and guarantee initiative sustainability over time.

Good practices in Italy

Among the good practices identified in Italy is the project "L'Altroparlante" coordinated by the University for Foreigners of Siena (CLUSS Center) and implemented in six Italian schools located in non-urban contexts characterised by a high presence of students with diverse migration backgrounds. The initiative promotes "translanguaging" which is a multilingual learning-based educational approach that goes beyond the intercultural approach and is integrated across the curriculum. Unlike the traditional approach of the Italian school system that promotes the

inexperience of education staff, as well as the lack of networks among schools, reception facilities, social services, training centres, and employment offices (Santagati and Barzaghi, 2021).

⁵⁷ This section briefly summarises the results of the analysis available in the publication IMMERSE (2022a). All 60 good practices can be explored in depth on IMMERSE's Online Digital Database <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/online-digital-database-of-good-practices-and-resources-in-social-integration-of-refugee-and-migrant-children/>

learning of Italian as a second language (L2) for more effective inclusion, these schools value the linguistic repertoires of students, recognizing their mother tongue as a key factor for inclusion and a democratic tool that offers equal opportunities for participation and expression.

6.4 Policy implications and recommendations

The results of IMMERSE quantitative and qualitative research activities describe the state of the art of the socio-educational integration process of minors with a migrant background in Italy and Europe, leading to reflections about the necessary intervention policies and actions at institutional and school level. To overcome the extreme heterogeneity of the approaches adopted on Italian territories, it is necessary to encourage the development of a univocal model of inclusion based on a more intentional and systematic approach, involving all key actors, and inspired by a vision of cultural diversity as a resource that benefits all.

We, therefore, urge the Parliament and Government, in accordance with the EU Institutions

- to adopt a European and national harmonised data collection system based on internationally accepted definitions, multidimensional indicators, and a common, co-creative and child-centred approach, such as the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators, to study the state of the art of the socio-educational integration of migrant-background minors in schools and non-formal education environments.
- to adopt a uniform model of integration, that guarantees standardisation as well as flexibility and adherence to local needs, adopting a child-centred approach. This requires the cooperation of all institutions/stakeholders involved in reception and integration and the systematisation of specific measures for distinct target groups expressing differentiated needs. Integration policies must be aligned with social, educational, urban, and economic policies and must be supported by long-term, financially stable funding solutions.

We recommend Parliament

- to reform Law no. 91 of 1992, guaranteeing the right to Italian citizenship for children born in Italy with parents who demonstrate stable legal residence in our country and facilitated paths to acquire Italian citizenship for minors growing up in Italy or who have arrived in Italy through family reunification.

We urge the Government and the Ministry of Education and Merit

- to reactivate the National Observatory for the integration of foreign students and for intercultural, established with Ministerial Decree no. 717 of 5 September 2014, in order to guarantee the fulfilment of its consultative and proactive role on school intercultural integration policies and to encourage, also through the allocation of adequate resources, the effective implementation of the Guidelines for intercultural orientation 2022.
- to allocate adequate economic resources and guarantee specialised professionals working in schools with a high presence of pupils with a migrant background, in order to enhance the linguistic and cultural heritage and make multicultural schools attractive. The work of cultural mediators should be guaranteed with stability throughout the whole educational path. In this regard, it is necessary to adopt clear comprehensive legislation to define the

profession of the intercultural mediator. Furthermore, schools must be equipped with adequate resources for Italian L2 courses and extra-curricular socialisation activities.

We recommend the Ministry of Education and Merit

- to ensure that, as part of the educational guidance reform envisaged by the PNRR (M4C1 - Reform 1.4) and the related Guidelines issued with Ministerial Decree no. 328 of 22 December 2022, guidance teachers are adequately trained in order to guarantee guidance activities that take into account the interests and talents of students and limit the risk of drop-out and early leaving. Educational guidance should be free from stereotypes and prejudices linked to the migration background, gender, or other conditions.
- to ensure the development of teachers' intercultural competences through both initial teacher education and in-service training. As recommended by the Guidelines for Intercultural Orientation (2022), Universities, while respecting their autonomy, should encourage the presence of intercultural pedagogy and teaching of the Italian language for foreigners. At the same time, as provided for by the Prime Ministerial Decree of 4 August 2023 (GU n.224 of 25-9-2023) which defines the teachers' minimum professional skills, it is necessary to guarantee qualifying academic courses for the initial training of secondary school teachers that promote intercultural teaching approaches and inclusive methodologies.

We recommend schools

- to guarantee full and equal access for all children to inclusive and quality education in the formal education system and the timely enrolment, even during the school year, of students with a migration background – especially UAMs – in classes corresponding to their age, in accordance with the provisions of the Consolidating Act on Immigration (Legislative Decree no. 286/1998), the Ministerial note no. 101 of 8 January 2010, the indications contained in the ministerial circulars on registrations⁵⁸ and the Guidelines for intercultural orientation (2022). At the same time, schools should guarantee social and geographical heterogeneity when creating class groups.
- to adopt teaching approaches that enhance education inclusiveness, interculturality, linguistic and cultural pluralism, also through the adoption of multilingual textbooks and teaching materials and the organisation of catch-up programmes and accelerated learning opportunities. Interventions should involve the whole educating community.
- to favour an inclusive school climate, which promotes student wellbeing and belonging and protects against instances of discrimination, bullying and exclusion of refugee and migrant children, through dedicated resources. Psycho-social support should be offered in schools to target the specific needs of migrant-background students.

We recommend national and local institutions, schools and the educating community

- to allocate adequate resources, guarantee the systematisation and support the upscaling of good practices at local, national, and European level, to promote a common model of integration, able to balance standardisation and flexibility, and favour the implementation of innovative practices in the field of education and social integration to also avoid school

⁵⁸ The most recent is the Ministerial circular prot. no. 33071 related to enrolment for the s.y. 2023/2024.

dropouts. Practices should adopt a multidimensional, holistic approach, offering multiple activities and collaborating with extra-school parties, critical public services (health, child protection, social protection, parental labour market support, etc.), interdisciplinary specialised professionals and heterogeneous networks. Projects should apply a child-centred, empowering, and inclusive approach, where migrant children are acknowledged as agents and the whole educating community is actively involved, strengthening opportunities for social participation.

- to safeguard UAMs' right to education by guaranteeing immediate access to formal education, flexible and highly personalised linguistic-educational offers, and professionals specifically trained to welcome UAMs. UAMs should be informed about education and integration opportunities. They should be listened to and their skills should be enhanced through an intercultural and child-centred approach.

We urge local public administrations:

- to ensure that families in difficult socio-economic conditions can effectively access services and curricular and extracurricular activities (e.g. support measures for the purchase of books, canteen and transport services, school trips, sports activities, scholarships, and access to kindergarten), without discrimination based on the citizenship status or registered residence, pursuant to art. 38 of Legislative Decree no. 286/98.

Children's recommendations for inclusive schools and societies

To promote their empowerment and enhance their key role in defining their own path of inclusion, children and adolescents were involved in policy consultation activities, in order to formulate a specific proposal through a co-creation method⁵⁹.

Children and adolescents ask for a more inclusive school based on:

- equal rights and opportunities for all students;
- the innovation of pedagogy, with more supportive, trained teachers – also with a migrant background – and inclusive didactic methods, capable of enhancing students' background (culture, language, etc.), competences, and talents;
- the availability of cultural mediators and materials in different languages to also facilitate the involvement of families and communities;
- intercultural education, as part of the school curriculum, to learn different cultures and enhance the background of each classmate;
- child-friendly spaces and opportunities to socialise with peers during school time and extra school time.

6.5 Conclusions

With the increasing number of students with migrant backgrounds, in the last decades the Italian school system has been particularly engaged with the challenge of integration and interculturality.

⁵⁹ As for Italy, Save the Children conducted policy consultation activities with children in Prato and Marghera, two towns where the Organisation works to prevent and contrast educational poverty through the implementation of its programme "Punti Luce" (Spotlight). A "Punto Luce" is a child-friendly educative space, often located in the most vulnerable neighbourhoods, which offers accessible, free-of-charge educative and training activities to children aged 6 to 17.

The IMMERSE quantitative research results and qualitative studies have made a critical contribution revealing the state of the art of the socio-educational integration path of migrant and refugee children from a multidimensional perspective, stressing the challenges and opportunities that they experience in Italy. Despite the commitment of educational staff and many good practices at local level, the scarcity and inadequacy of organisational, economic, and professional resources weaken the efficacy of interventions, both at school and in the community. Migrant-background children – especially UAMs – strive to access education and other key social services, are exposed to the risk of drop-out, and suffer from discrimination, bullying, and poor social relationships with peers, teachers, and the community. These are factors that negatively affect children’s happiness and sense of belonging. IMMERSE data highlight the need for a radical shift in policies and intervention approaches. To encourage the development of a univocal model of inclusion based on a more intentional and systematic approach, existing good practices and guidelines for the integration of migrant-background children need to be effectively implemented. It is necessary to adequately train professionals and enhance innovative didactic methods, involving all key actors through networks and guaranteeing sufficient funds. Starting from the abovementioned policy recommendations, it is paramount that institutions and the education system commit to improving the socio-educational integration of migrant-background children, acknowledging and protecting their fundamental rights.

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7 National recommendations paper – Spain: The socio-educational integration of migrant-background children in Spain: evidence and policy proposals from the IMMERSE project

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7.1 Executive summary

This report aims to summarise the main activities carried out in the framework of IMMERSE⁶⁰, an EU Commission-funded H2020 research project aiming to enhance the socio-educative inclusion of refugee and migrant children in Europe. The focus here will be on the work undertaken in Spain in order to offer a series of policy recommendations that, based on the results obtained, will inform policymakers and the educational system with specific recommendations related to the socio-educational integration of migrant-background children in schools and other learning environments.

7.2 The Spanish context

In the shift between the 20th to the 21st century, the migratory trends in Spain reversed, becoming a net receiving country of immigrants. As a result of the increasing number of migrants and their progressive integration into Spanish society, the total number of migrant minors enrolled in the educational system has risen as well, reaching approximately 10% of the student body in 2021 (EDUCAbase, 2022).

According to the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training of Spain (2022), this percentage represents 854,121 students across public and private educational centres. However, these official numbers often do not reflect other profiles of migrant children and adolescents, such as refugee, asylum-seeking, or unaccompanied minors (EDUCAbase, 2022). As they tend to arrive at middle or late adolescence, their opportunities to become enrolled in formal education decrease, and they are at a higher stake of enrolling in vocational training and non-formal education (mainly through language learning courses) (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2019).

The previous research on the socio-educational integration of migrant students in Spain shows the persistent inequalities that these students experience, leading to higher rates of Early School Leaving (ESL) (European Commission, 2015), lower academic achievement (OECD, 2016), and lower educational attainment at tertiary educational levels (Eurostat, 2022).

⁶⁰ <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/>

While Spain is a party member of international conventions such as the Geneva Convention or Convention on the Rights of the Child, it has not developed specific legislation or policies for integrating migrant and refugee children. As Gómez Fernández and Pérez González (2017) explain, foreigners' rights in Spain, whether adults or children are regulated by the Organic Law 4/2000 of 11 January 2000 on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration. There, together with the Spanish Constitution, the Law 12/2009, of 30 October, regulating the right to asylum and subsidiary protection, and the Organic Law 1/1996 of 15 January 1996 on the Legal Protection of Minors, partially amending the Civil Code and the Civil Procedure Act it is specified that minors have the right to education and health independently of their administrative situation. They have also been granted protection against *refoulement* and a comprehensive right to information (in an understandable language) on the content of their status. In political terms, the Spanish State has not developed a national integration plan for foreigners (either adults or minors) (Cebolla-Boado and González-Ferrer, 2014), but some Autonomous Communities have their own. The case of unaccompanied minors is different, as in 2021, the Royal Decree 903/2021 of 19 October amending the Regulation of Organic Law 4/2000 on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration, following its reform by Organic Law 2/2009, approved by Royal Decree 557/2011 of 20 April protected this group from falling into irregularity by easing, among other aspects, the obtention of a work permit once they become adults.

While the number of migrant children residing in Spain has exponentially grown over time, representing about 10% of total students in formal schools, the fact that they are three times more exposed to Early School Leaving (ESL) (European Commission, 2015) compared to natives shows that the Spanish State still needs to make more efforts to improve their situation. A national policy for migrant children integration is required. While granting their access to education and health no matter their administrative situation, as well as protecting them from *refoulement* constitutes a positive basis, specific legislation, as it has been done recently (with the Royal Decree 903/2021) for the case of unaccompanied minors, is a need. Migrant and refugee children are among the most vulnerable social groups, so decisive State action is fundamental for ensuring their integration and reducing inequalities that may potentially become chronic in Spanish society.

7.3 IMMERSE project: evidence-based considerations and critical issues

IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators

The main contribution of the IMMERSE project is the development of a new system of indicators that synthesizes the diverse social realities of the European countries into harmonic measures which reflect it conceptually and empirically. Other previous systems of indicators have addressed the integration of migrants in Europe: The Migration Policy Index or the Zaragoza indicators are good examples in this regard (Huddleston et al. 2011). However, these previous systems of indicators are not fully applicable to children for several reasons: first, the target population that they aim to assess and monitor are adults, and therefore specific areas key for the children's future opportunities, development, and life trajectories are not contemplated; and second, the scope of these systems of indicators tend to be limited to the objective macro socio-cultural and economic aspects of the social life, which in the case of migrant children, overlooks the ecological factors that influence their growth in time (Bajo Marcos et al., 2023). The lack of a child-centred and systemic perspective in the previous systems of indicators prevents accurately evaluating

children's realities and justifies the need to develop the IMMERSE system of socio-educational integration indicators.

Upon this basis, the new system of indicators⁶¹ was built applying a co-creative methodology that included iterative consultations of children and other relevant stakeholders at different stages. The resulting system allows assessing five dimensions of integration results in children (access to rights, language and culture, well-being, social connectedness, and educational achievement) along with different factors at the meso and macro levels acting as barriers or facilitators of the integration process (Fernández García et al., 2020). These indicators allow a comparative overview of the degree of integration experienced by children in different countries, monitoring its evolution in time and identifying areas of future intervention in a given context. A literature review, the implementation of qualitative case studies, and a systematic collection of good practices have complemented the overall picture the IMMERSE project aims to give on migrant and refugee children integration.

Qualitative insights

The first qualitative fieldwork aimed at identifying key indicators of the educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children through understanding the role of intercultural competencies and multilingualism with relevant stakeholders in the socio-educational field at three levels. First, at the micro level, four workshops were conducted with refugee and migrant children aged 6-18 years, and one workshop with parents of these children. Second, at the meso level, one workshop (World Café) was organized with 25 educators and representatives working within the field of migrant services. And finally, at the macro level, six individual interviews were carried out with policymakers and experts in education and/or integration.

The results of this qualitative work indicated that two significant facilitators related to intercultural integration are:

- The presence of supportive close bridges with natives that integrate the children into the host society.
- The creation of intercultural educational environments that foster and train intercultural skills of children and adolescents.

Among the main identified needs, participants highlighted the importance of studying the access to social and communitarian services, and, as for the school-life dimension, the impact of possible negative attitudes and discrimination towards migrants was identified as a key dimension.

Data collection results for Spain

For the present report, we analysed the data gathered on 5,802 children aged 10-18 and 1,397 children aged 7-9, accounting for 7,199 children in total. Among them, 39% were non-migrant, 34% second-generation and 18% first-generation migrant children. Slightly above half of them were male (51%), less than half were female (46%) and a very small amount (2%) described their gender in

⁶¹ For details about the composition of the dashboard consult <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/selection-and-creation-of-dashboard-of-socio-educational-integration-indicators/>
Online access to the public dashboard is available <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/immerse-dashboard-of-indicators-on-refugee-and-migrant-children-integration/>

another way, accounting for 130 children in this group. The description of the 60 sites was gathered through the participation of 36 principals and the teaching staff of the centres.

Concerning language, most migrant-background children in Spain (87%) declare a high competence in Spanish, well above any other IMMERSE country. Probably, this is due to the large share of Spanish-speaking migrants (32% over migrant children excluding those with migrant background), which may also be connected to the fact that a large majority (60%) of migrant-background children declare a high level of belonging in their schools, a notably higher result than the average and the highest result across IMMERSE countries.

Regarding cultural identity patterns, almost half of the first- (49%) and second-generation (46%) migrant-background children in Spain feel close to both their cultures of origin and others from the host society and transversal categories. Practically the same share of first- (41%) and second-generation migrant children (48%) does not feel close to their cultures of origin.

About the support they feel they receive, nearly two-thirds of the migrant-background children in Spain declare high support from teachers (68%), friends, and peers (61%). This is well above the average and the highest result across IMMERSE countries. However, this last dimension notably diminishes per migrant background: from native children (74%) to second-generation migrant children (64%) and first-generation migrant children (56%). There are no significant differences between boys and girls; however, while discussing support, trust, and a sense of belonging, results tend to be notably inferior for those who define their gender “in another way”. The most shocking dimension is unhappiness, where these children present a much higher percentage (43%) than boys (15%) and girls (19%).

Age is also a fundamental dimension. Among migrant-background children, the percentage of those with a high level of belonging at school notably diminishes as they grow: from 76% of small children to 55% of early adolescents and 49-50% among middle and late adolescents. The same for trusting teachers and schools, which dramatically diminishes with age: from 95% of small children to 73% of early adolescents, and further to 54% among middle and late adolescents.

One-third of the migrant-background children in Spain who participated to the survey (33%) avoid places for fear of being badly treated, and, among them, the share is significantly higher for those who declare their gender as “another way” (57% compared to 29% for boys and 34% for girls). The same for those who have been victims of bullying; about one-third of boys and girls have suffered from it, but it affected more than half (54%) of those who defined themselves as “another way”.

Most school principals surveyed in Spain (86%) declare that intercultural values are one of the insignias of their schools. This is well above the average and the highest value among IMMERSE countries; however, less than half (48%) of teachers agree, even if all sites have 4 or 5 topics on intercultural values and competencies (a pattern only repeated in Italy), according to them.

Qualitative case studies in reception centres of unaccompanied minors

The target population of the two qualitative fieldworks in Spain were unaccompanied migrant minors. Two reception centres were visited: one in Lleida (Catalonia), which was the reference centre in the province and was ruled by a private organisation (Sant Joan de Deu), and the only public reception centre of Castilla la Mancha. While children in those centres had a similar profile, there was a considerable asymmetry regarding their social integration. As both centres depended

on different administrations (the Governments of their respective Autonomous Communities), there was a significant divergence regarding financing, program assistance and monitoring of results. It must also be said that both realities were despairing as Catalonia was the third hosting community in 2020 with 1168 children while Castilla La Mancha only hosted 75 (Sajir et al., 2022). While Lleida's centre had several language and professional training programs and accommodations for children over 18 to ensure they are not left alone after reaching legal age, in Castilla la Mancha, becoming an adult implied exiting the reception system without further assistance. Unaccompanied minors are highly vulnerable, and the lack of specific national (or autonomous) integration plans threatens their future. In Lleida, Sant Joan de Deu has developed its own system focusing on training the minors they host in language and labour skills and accompanying them into adulthood with the aim of maximising their chances of getting a job. Compared to Castilla la Mancha, the results from this model show the importance of helping these children integrate into social networks, allowing them to have a normal life in Spain.

Good Practices

Ten good practices were identified in Spain and were evaluated through a comparative analysis at the European level: Abraza África / Misión Emmanuel, Egeria Program - For the inclusion of immigrant students in intercultural schools, FRIDA Project - Training for the prevention and detection of racism and xenophobia in the classroom, In Crescendo, Kairós Majadahonda Association - Care and support for children and teenagers at risk of social exclusion and their families, Multitasking Cooperative Classrooms, Project "Integral attention to children" - Tomillo Foundation, Projecte Rossinyol - Intercultural youth mentoring programme in Spain, Prollema - Empowering young migrants to teach their mother tongue, and Sant Joan de Déu Terres in Lleida - Almacelles. Additionally, two of them were analysed in-depth as case studies: the FRIDA Project and the previously mentioned Sant Joan de Déu Terres (Lleida) centre for unaccompanied minors (UAMs). The [IMMERSE Online Digital Database](#) provides an extensive description of the 60 European initiatives.

In terms of *efficacy*, each proposed good practice has found one or more correspondences in the project Dashboards of indicators. Some aim to guarantee refugee and migrant children's access to and completion of compulsory and non-compulsory education, while others attempt to promote improvement in their academic abilities. Moreover, most of them aim to improve children's competence in the language of the host country and try to guarantee that children preserve their cultural identity while adopting new cultural values and intercultural competencies; they also focus on increasing children's integration by improving their relationships with friends and peers, and on their relationships with teachers and trust in institutions (e.g., schools, police, hospitals). Nearly all of them seek to increase children's sense of belonging and focus on children's happiness and life satisfaction.

Regarding *efficiency*, most initiatives involve more than one category of professionals (mainly from educational, academic, research, and social sectors) and can activate a diversified network of stakeholders, such as governmental and local authorities, school communities, NGOs, universities, and research centers.

Concerning *reproducibility and transferability*, almost all projects have activated communication tools to promote the dissemination of the project's results and the effective transfer of experiences

and methodologies. Additionally, most of them have been replicated or have the potential to be transferred to different contexts.

Regarding *political relevance*, some receive European and governmental funds, and others receive private funds (foundations, donations, etc.). Most are connected with local authorities over national and supranational entities regarding networking and/or partnership with political or administrative authorities.

7.4 Policy implications and recommendations

Although presenting positive results and initiatives in general, the evidence collected through the survey, the qualitative fieldwork and the good practices analysis suggest the need for specific policies and effective intervention actions.

We, therefore, recommend:

- the Spanish Government and the Autonomous Communities to develop a National Intercultural Integration Plan for immigrant children. They must elaborate a proposal starting from schools with the cooperation of principals and teachers, able to strengthen children's trust towards institutions and protect them from discriminatory actions. Plans should also include a gender dimension. We believe that a systematised intercultural education (Fernández and Molinero-Gerbeau, 2021) has to be part of a broad National Integration Strategic plan for migrants.
- the Ministry of Education to transversally adopt an intercultural frame in its national education policies, based on active socialisation processes promoting language learning and avoiding school segregation. It is crucial to implicate families, teachers, and principals for developing feelings of belonging, minimising intra-familial conflicts and creating bridges with the host society. The Ministry shall develop provisions with specifically allocated economic resources in the national education law to ensure that promoting the socialisation of migrant and refugee children is legally guaranteed.
- the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration to develop a national integration plan for unaccompanied minors containing specific funds to set up training and labour market inclusion programs in every reception centre of the country. Unaccompanied minors should be considered as a concrete group when becoming adults; their situation should not be regulated by the general migration legislation but by a specific law defining their status as children to be protected with minimum standards (granting accommodation, income, and access to education and the labour market) also when becoming adults.
- the Ministry of Education to adopt a national intercultural educational program in cooperation with the social, academic, and educational actors. The experience of the analysed practices revealed the need to reshape the Spanish education system by transversally adopting an intercultural view. Language classes, curricular and extracurricular activities, vocational and educational training, school models shaping, network building, and advocacy initiatives to integrate migrant and refugee children are fundamental. The current frame only focuses on access to school, but children's sense of belonging, happiness, and life satisfaction are as fundamental as this in order to avoid school dropout, which, as it is well-known, may derive into broader social problems in the future.

Children's recommendations for inclusive schools and societies

Children in the consultation activities provided additional recommendations targeted at the school and policy levels.

For schools:

- Organise talks to promote empathy with migrants and reduce harassment.
- Organise intercultural thematic journeys for sharing cultural values.
- Pay specific attention to newcomers and group them in the same classes so they can help each other.

For policymakers

- Facilitate access to regular status for every migrant, so parents may work without limitations and visit their countries of origin to avoid losing contact with their families and friends.
- Give regular status to children when they enrol in school.
- Politicians should visit schools to listen to them and understand the problems of migrant children.

7.5 Conclusions

The IMMERSE Project has proved to be essential to understand a social reality that is as relevant as it is hidden. The implementation of the various methodologies, notably the dashboard but also the qualitative studies, has revealed the existence of numerous undetected realities that are at the origin of some of the main problems suffered by migrant and refugee children, such as school dropout, bullying or the lack of a sense of belonging to the place of residence. The data show a strong need to develop national plans to make the Spanish education system intercultural, but this requires a decided political will and specific funding. Some groups of migrant children, such as unaccompanied minors, have seen their situation improve thanks to recent legislative changes, but specific actions are required that seek not only to guarantee legal residence and access to essential social services but also to pursue broader social integration. This requires the involvement of the whole educational community along with social and academic actors as well as professionals in charge of reception centres for unaccompanied minors. The IMMERSE project makes a decisive contribution to providing specific evidence for tackling the complex challenges that plague the socio-educational integration of migrant and refugee minors. This set of policy recommendations also aims to influence the political reality by providing proposals that, according to the research teams in charge of the analyses, would help to put the situation decisively back on track.

7.6 References

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